

FLOATFARM

NEXT GENERATION FLOATING WIND FARMS

DELIVERABLE D3.1

Validated wake model for QBlade
capable of modeling turbine interactions

J. Saverin, Ang Li, Fanzhong Meng

June 2025

Document Track Information

Project information	
Project title	Developing the Next Generation of Environmentally-Friendly Floating Wind Farms with Innovative Technologies and Sustainable Solutions
Starting date	01.01.2024
Duration	48 months
Programme	HORIZON EUROPE
Call identifier	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01
Grant Agreement No	101136091

Deliverable information	
Deliverable number	3.1
Work package number	3
Deliverable title	Validated wake model for QBlade capable of modeling turbine interactions
Lead beneficiary	Delft Technical University
Author	Joseph Saverin, Ang Li, Fanzhong Meng
Due date	30.06.2025
Actual submission date	30.06.2025
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

Revision information			
Version	Contributors	Date	Description
v1	JS,AL,FM	15.06.25	First draft
v1.1	G. Vaz	25.06.25	Review 1
v2.1	JS	28.06.25	Second Draft
v2.2	JS	21.10.25	Corrected disclaimer

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

About FLOATFARM

The **FLOATFARM** project is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe program. This project is closely linked to the **FLOATECH** project (2020-2023) and aims to bring the technologies developed within FLOATECH to the next level of technological readiness, complementing them with a significant number of new concepts, innovations and methods. **FLOATFARM** aims to significantly advance the maturity and competitiveness of floating offshore wind (FOW) technology by increasing energy production, achieving significant cost reductions within the design and implementation phases, improving offshore wind value chain and supporting EU companies in this growing sector. Additionally, **FLOATFARM** aims to decrease negative environmental impacts on marine life and to enhance the public acceptability of FOW, thereby accelerating the EU energy transition. The **FLOATFARM** consortium is coordinated by the Technische Universität Berlin and is made up of 17 partners spread across 8 countries, each contributing to technology and scientific excellence in the wind energy sector.

The approach of **FLOATFARM** can be broken down into three actions:

1. Turbine Technology: Development of innovative technologies and methods for improvements on an individual FOW turbine level,
2. Farm Technology: Development, investigation and demonstration of technologies that are applicable to an array of turbines within a FOW farm,
3. Environmental & Socioeconomic Impacts: Model development, data collection and scenario analysis of environmental, economic and sociological impacts of FOW farms.

CONTENTS

1 Introduction	4
2 Methodology	6
2.1 Field Equations	6
2.1.1 Velocity Field	6
2.1.2 Evolution of Vorticity	6
2.2 Vortex Particle Representation	7
2.3 Vortex Particle-Mesh method	7
2.4 Numerical Implementation	8
2.4.1 MIRAS	9
2.4.2 HAWC2	10
2.4.3 SailFFish	11
2.4.4 QBlade	15
3 Solver Verification and Validation	16
3.1 SailFFish Verification: Vortex ring flows	16
3.1.1 Unbounded Vortical Flow: Viscous Vortex Rings	16
3.2 Code to Code comparison: SailFFish and MIRAS	20
3.2.1 Comparison setup: IEA 10MW RWT	20
3.2.2 Rotor aerodynamic performance	23
3.2.3 Convergence study of the flow field	26
3.2.4 Wake induction and flow fields	29
3.2.5 Statistics: wake recovery and wake turbulence	33
3.2.6 Discussion	35
3.3 Comparison: SailFFish and OJF Data	35
3.3.1 Comparison setup: MoWiTO Turbine	35
3.3.2 Convergence study	39
3.3.3 Wake induction and flow fields	42
3.3.4 Statistics: wake recovery and wake turbulence	46
3.3.5 Discussion	47
4 Application	48
4.1 Helix Excitation	48
4.1.1 Dynamic Wake Behaviour	48
4.1.2 Increased wake recovery	49
4.2 Multiple turbine interaction	51
4.2.1 Baseline case	53
4.2.2 Helix case	53
5 Conclusion	55
References	56

1 INTRODUCTION

Offshore winds are typically stronger and more steady. To fully exploit potential wind resources, there is growing interest in deploying wind turbines on floating platforms in deep waters. The transition from onshore to floating offshore environments implies a significant change in the nature of the wind resource, increasing aerodynamic interaction between turbines in offshore wind farms. In the offshore environment wind is steadier and has lower turbulence levels than in the onshore case, where the inflow is influenced by microscale effects of the terrain around the wind farm. This leads to increased stability of the wake structures, which implies that these structures persist longer and the probability of interaction with the downstream turbines increases [1]. This interaction has been demonstrated to give rise to greater levels of unsteady loading, contributing to reduced blade lifetime and increased drivetrain wear [2]. Furthermore, turbines operating in the wake of an upstream turbine generate reduced power due to the decreased energy flux through the rotor. The exploitation of innovative farm control strategies tailored for Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWTs) can help mitigate this effect.

An attractive approach, which is being explored to the aforementioned challenge, is to excite fluid-dynamic instabilities in the turbine wake in order to accelerate wake breakdown. This method is referred to as active wake mixing. This leads to an accelerated wake recovery, which results in more a more uniform inflow for downstream turbines. A second possible approach, which may be combined with active wake excitation, is to exploit the compliance of the mooring system to displace the turbine platform away from a given equilibrium position and thereby translate the wake region.

The potential approaches mentioned above need accurate aerodynamic modeling to enable capturing the changes of velocity and vorticity fields in the wake of an upstream wind turbine. In order to accurately model unsteady aerodynamic interactions between turbines, a numerical treatment is required which captures the unsteadiness and local dynamical nature of the wake. This model must be capable of capturing realistically the velocity field in the wake during the process of breakdown and recovery. A suitable model is the velocity-vorticity model implemented in the MIRAS solver developed at DTU [3]. It is coupled to the aero-hydro-servo-elastic simulation tool HAWC2 (Horizontal Axis Wind turbine simulation Code 2nd generation) [4], also developed by DTU, to enable aero-elastic simulations of multiple turbines and capture the wake interactions between turbines.

This report presents the work carried out by TU Berlin and DTU in Task 3.1 focusing on the development, the implementation and the verification of the new

open-source wake model SailFFish [5]. The report is organized into four sections. Section 2 describes the methodology behind the vortex-based model. In Section 3 the verification of the model against MIRAS using the IEA 10 MW reference wind turbine (RWT) [6] will be presented, followed by its validation using experimental data from the MOWITO-0.6 turbine [7], tested at the Open Jet Facility (OJF) in TU Delft. Finally, Section 4 discusses application case studies where SailFFish is used to simulate helix excitation, with the aim of investigating fast wake recovery and multi-turbine interactions.

2 METHODOLOGY

The formulation of the flow solvers employed in this report will be described here. First, the field equations which are used to describe the evolution of the flow field are described. Following this, vortex particles will be described followed by the vortex particle-mesh method. Finally, the numerical implementation will be described.

2.1 Field Equations

It is assumed that the flow is incompressible and consisting entirely of a Newtonian fluid. Position is denoted with the vector \vec{x} and time with the symbol t . An implicit assumption is hereafter made that all variables are a function of both space and time. The main dependent variable of the methodology employed here is the vorticity field $\vec{\omega}$, defined as the curl of the velocity field at any point: $\vec{\omega} = \nabla \times \vec{u}$.

2.1.1 Velocity Field

It can be shown that a twice continuously differentiable vector field can be expressed as the sum of an irrotational scalar potential Φ and a divergence-free vector potential $\vec{\psi}$ [8]. This is expressed here for the velocity field:

$$\vec{u} = -\nabla\Phi + \nabla \times \vec{\psi} = \vec{U}_{\infty} + \nabla \times \vec{\psi}. \quad (2.1)$$

The vector potential $\vec{\psi}$ is generally referred to as the stream function. \vec{U}_{∞} represents the ambient freestream flow. Assuming that the inflow is irrotational, taking the curl of the above equation results in the Poisson equation:

$$\nabla^2 \vec{\psi} = -\vec{\omega}, \quad (2.2)$$

which directly links vorticity to the stream function of the flow. By taking the curl of this equation and assuming a standard gauge condition, the velocity field can be directly expressed as:

$$\nabla^2 \vec{u} = -\nabla \times \vec{\omega}, \quad (2.3)$$

which is a Poisson equation relating the velocity and vorticity fields.

2.1.2 Evolution of Vorticity

By nature of its definition, it follows that the vorticity is divergence-free:

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{\omega} = 0. \quad (2.4)$$

Assuming that the body forces acting on the fluid are irrotational, taking the curl of the Navier-Stokes equations gives the vorticity transport equation (VTE):

$$\frac{d\vec{\omega}}{dt} = \frac{\partial\vec{\omega}}{\partial t} + (\vec{u} \cdot \nabla)\vec{\omega} = (\vec{\omega} \cdot \nabla)\vec{u} + \nu \nabla^2\vec{\omega}. \quad (2.5)$$

2.2 Vortex Particle Representation

In the vortex particle method, the spatial distribution of vorticity is defined as the sum of a set of vortex particles, each having vorticity $\vec{\omega}_p$ and occupying a volume dv_p , representing an incremental circulation $\vec{\alpha}_p = \vec{\omega}_p dv_p$:

$$\vec{\omega}(\vec{x}) := \sum_p \vec{\omega}_p \delta(\vec{x} - \vec{x}_p), \quad (2.6)$$

where δ is the 3D Dirac delta function. The evolution of the particle set is treated in a Lagrangian sense, implying the particle positions and strengths are tracked, rather than being defined within a spatially constant grid.

Particle motion is specified through the kinematic definition:

$$\frac{d\vec{x}_p}{dt} = \vec{u}(\vec{x}_p). \quad (2.7)$$

Inspecting the VTE in Eq. (2.5), the evolution of particle strength is seen to be composed of two contributions. The first term $(\vec{\omega} \cdot \nabla)\vec{u}$ is a consequence of the divergence-free nature of the vorticity field and represents the change in vorticity which occurs when the vortex is sheared or strained. The second term $\nu \nabla^2\vec{\omega}$ is the change due to viscous diffusion. There are numerous approaches to calculating these terms.

2.3 Vortex Particle-Mesh method

In the vortex particle-mesh (VPM) method, a combined Lagrangian-Eulerian approach is applied whereby the principle flow quantity is the vorticity field, defined on a grid of Lagrangian particles. At each timestep, this vorticity field is mapped to a fixed (Eulerian) cartesian grid defined on a 3D rectangular flow domain. This mapping procedure is visualised for simplicity for a 1D case in Fig. 1. All flow quantities, including velocity, gradients of vorticity, molecular and turbulent shear stresses are calculated on the Eulerian grid. In order to advance the particle field, flow quantities at the Lagrangian positions are interpolated from the Eulerian grid.

This process substantially is composed of four steps:

- i) Lagrangian vorticity markers (particles) positions are mapped to the regular grid with a chosen mapping function.

Figure 1. The mapping between a Lagrangian grid node and an Eulerian grid node illustrated for simplicity on a 1D grid with a single row of cells. Each dashed line represents a mapping factor which represents the contribution of the Lagrangian node to the surrounding Eulerian nodes as a function of the displacement distance.

- ii) Eq. (2.3) is solved on the Eulerian grid for the resolution of the velocity field \vec{u} using a Poisson solver.
- iii) Eq. (2.5) is applied to calculate gradients of the velocity and vorticity fields on the Eulerian grid.
- iv) Flow quantities are interpolated to the Lagrangian positions and the particle field is advanced in time.

Mapping Functions: Mapping of flow field quantities between the Lagrangian and Eulerian fields can be accomplished with a mapping function $M(x)$. These are formulated such that the spatial moments of vorticity are preserved up to order m : $\vec{\Omega} = \vec{\omega} x^m$. A set of common symmetric mapping functions are shown in Fig. 2: The

Figure 2. Mapping functions to transfer quantities from Lagrangian particle positions to a regular grid of cell width H: d is the distance to the neighboring grid point. The mapping type and order (in parenthesis) are given.

mapping functions are generally one-dimensional and symmetric $M(x)$. For mapping in higher dimensions a tensor product is taken $M_{x,y,z} = M(x) M(y) M(z)$. These mapping functions have the additional advantage that they can be used not only for mapping to the grid, but also for interpolating results from the grid. A visualisation of a mapped vorticity field is given in Fig. 3.

2.4 Numerical Implementation

The implementation of the numerical tools used in this report are described below.

Figure 3. An x - y plane of a dense vortex ring. The ω_y field is shown corresponding to the mapped vorticity field. The Lagrangian field is shown with points and the mapped Eulerian field as a contour.

2.4.1 MIRAS

MIRAS (Method for Interactive Rotor Aerodynamic Simulations) [3, 9] is a multi-fidelity in-house aerodynamic code developed at DTU for simulating the unsteady flow and rotor aerodynamics of wind turbines. It is based on the vortex theory, providing detailed modeling of the bound, trailed and shed vorticities of the rotor and is capable of capturing both the wake evolution and wake interactions between multiple turbines. Two main computational strategies for wake modeling are implemented in MIRAS: the filament-only method and the hybrid filament-particle-mesh method.

Filament-Only Method

In the filament-only approach, the rotor blades are represented by discrete bound vortex filaments that both trail and shed vortex filaments as a result of spanwise and temporal variations in the bound circulation during rotor rotation. The evolution of these filaments is computed using the Biot-Savart law, which directly calculates the interaction, which is termed induction effects, between every filament element. This approach has relative high accuracy and is suitable for resolving near-wake dynamics and capturing blade-wake interactions. However, as the wake size grows and the number of filaments increases, the computational effort increases quadratically. As a result, the vortex filament method is impractical for long simulations, such as interactions between multiple turbines within a wind farm. Furthermore,

vortex filaments are based on potential flow theory and are therefore not suitable for the treatment of shear layer development or turbulent diffusion, both important processes in wake breakdown and recovery.

Hybrid Filament–Particle–Mesh Method

To further improve computational efficiency while still accurately modeling the blade's bound vortex and the near wake, MIRAS incorporates a hybrid filament–particle–mesh method. This approach combines the fidelity of direct filament interactions in the near wake with the computational efficiency of a mesh-based solver in the far wake. The vortex particle module, *pmlib*, developed in-house at DTU [10, 11], is integrated into MIRAS for this purpose. As the wake is convected downstream, the vortex filaments are transformed into vortex particles. These particles are then interpolated onto a structured Cartesian mesh, reconstructing the vorticity field. The induced velocity field is computed efficiently by solving a Poisson equation in Fourier space using a high-order regularized Green's function [10, 11]. The velocity field on the mesh is then interpolated back to the Lagrangian particle markers, allowing the continued evolution of the wake. The mesh-based treatment of the far wake greatly reduces computational costs and the code is parallelized using the Message Passing Interface (MPI) for high-performance computing.

Compared to the full filament method, the hybrid approach achieves a substantial reduction in computational cost while maintaining comparable accuracy in rotor loading and wake prediction. This enables the efficient simulation of the wake development after a turbine and wake interactions between multiple wind turbines, which are important for the analysis and optimization of floating wind farms.

2.4.2 HAWC2

HAWC2 is a multi-body beam-element aero-hydro-servo-elastic simulation tool for wind turbines, developed at DTU and distributed under both commercial and academic licenses [12]. The code is built upon an augmented floating frame of reference (FFR) formulation, enabling the modeling of the motion of flexible turbine components relative to an inertial frame. Structural components are discretized using Timoshenko beam elements and are connected via constraint equations, allowing the simulation of geometrically nonlinear deformations under aerodynamic, hydrodynamic, and control-induced loads. Time integration is carried out using a Newmark-beta scheme, which provides stable and accurate simulations of complex floating wind turbine systems.

Aerodynamic Modeling and Coupling to MIRAS

In addition to the standard unsteady polar-grid-based blade element momentum (BEM) method [13] that is implemented in HAWC2, aerodynamic solvers with higher

fidelity are available, such as the Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) CFD solver EllipSys3D and the multi-fidelity vortex solver MIRAS. The coupling is performed through a Python-based interface (referred to as the DTU coupling), which manages the exchange of data between the aerodynamic solver and the hydro-servo-elastic modules of HAWC2. At each time step, HAWC2 provides the blade kinematics to MIRAS, which computes the corresponding aerodynamic loads. These loads are then transferred back to HAWC2, replacing those from the built-in BEM module.

Because of differences in reference frames and discretization schemes between the solvers, the coupling process requires a set of detailed transformation matrices. These transformations are necessary to ensure a consistent and accurate mapping of velocities and aerodynamic loads between the coordinate systems used in MIRAS and HAWC2. Careful implementation of these transformations of forces and velocities between different coordinate systems is essential to achieve high accuracy in both aerodynamic load prediction and the structural response.

Application of the MIRAS-HAWC2 Framework

In the present study, all components of the wind turbine, including the tower and blades, are assumed to be rigid, which means the aeroelastic effects are neglected. However, the coupled MIRAS-HAWC2 framework is still used, as it facilitates convenient post-processing and streamlined simulation workflow. It should be noted that the coupled MIRAS-HAWC2 framework enables simulation of floating wind turbines under realistic environmental and control conditions. This framework allows for the inclusion of effects that are critical for floating offshore wind turbines, such as unsteady inflow, blade flexibility, controller actuation, platform motion, hydrodynamic forces and mooring system dynamics [1, 2].

2.4.3 SailFFish

SailFFish is an open-source fast Poisson solver written in C++ and `cuda` for solving Eq. (2.2) on Cartesian grids. The library can accept a range of boundary conditions including Dirichlet, Neumann, Periodic and unbounded problems and a range of options for the unbounded Green’s functions are available [14]. The core of the solution routine within SailFFish is the conversion of the problem to the frequency domain, where the convolution of the Green’s function is applied to reduce the computational expense. The fast Fourier transform (FFT) can be applied to efficiently move between time- and frequency-space representations. The solver is prepared such the FFT back-end can be exchanged based on the available hardware. Two options are provided as default: the popular FFTW library [15] or the `cuda` library `cuFFT` [16] for execution on NVidia graphics processing units (GPU).

The source code is available over the GitHub platform [5]. The baseline solver

has the functionality to directly resolve Eq. (2.3) for a given input field, making it suitable as the basis for a VPM-type solver. This has been carried out here and the functionality has been encapsulated in the *VPM_Solver* class which has been derived from the *Unbounded_Solver_3DV* class, where 3DV refers to three-dimensional vector input/output. An overview of the functioning of the solver is given in the following paragraphs.

2.4.3.1 Implementation

All grid and particle quantities are stored on discrete arrays. For example: The array representing the vorticity on the Eulerian grid $e_{u,o}$ is stored as three arrays floating-points values of length n , the total number of grid nodes in the domain. The simulation is started with n Lagrangian particles, aligned with the positions of the Eulerian grid nodes. As the simulation advances, the Lagrangian particles are displaced and their vorticity is updated according to Eq.s (2.3) and (2.5). A displacement vector l_d represents the deflection of each Lagrangian particle from its Eulerian position. Gradient data is stored in an equivalent manner. This allows for a state-space style representation which makes implementation of various time integration schemes straight-forward.

As the majority of the operations required for resolution of the grid are independent of neighboring nodes, the *VPM_Solver* is formulated with a Kernel-based architecture for grid and particle operations. This implies that each grid operation is formulated as a kernel acting on a grid node. This allows the kernel to be executed in parallel for each grid node, exploiting either multiprocessor capabilities (CPU) or *cuda/OpenCL* parallelism (GPU).

Monolithic and Block-ordered data When *SailFFish* is configured for CPU-execution, grid data is organized in a row-major format, referred to as a monolithic ordering. As accesses from CPU devices have generally very low latency, this architecture does not impact performance. In contrast to this, the order of data access in GPU kernels can have a drastic impact on performance due to misaligned reading from global data into local data. To exploit coalesced reading, the data is order into blocks, which correspond to dimensions of the GPU work groups. This is illustrated graphically in Fig 4.

Mapping and Interpolation: At the beginning of each time step, the vorticity is mapped to the Eulerian grid using a user-defined mapping kernel. A range of options are available including M_2 , M_4 , M_4' , M_6' [17]. Mapping kernels are defined for these tasks which operate over the entire field and map based on nearest neigh-

Figure 4. Data layout types in the VPM solver developed. Left: Monolithic layout. Right: Block layout.

bors. For block-ordered data, this is carried out by importing first the objective block into shared memory and then filling a halo of surrounding data depending on the required mapping stencil. Interpolation schemes are used after calculation of the grid gradients to specify gradients at the Lagrangian positions. As with the mapping, this is carried out by superposing contributions due to surrounding nodes an equivalent mapping scheme.

Grid Quantities: The quantities defined in Eq. (2.5) are calculated on the Eulerian grid at each time step using the finite differences. The order of the finite difference scheme applied is a user input and is available for 2nd, 4th, 6th and 8th-order differences. A central finite-difference scheme is used for all quantities and boundary nodes are skipped. Vorticity which passes over the boundary is simply removed from the domain.

Auxiliary functions A range of numerical features are required to ensure that the VPM scheme is robust. In order to ensure particle paths do not intersect, the Lagrangian particle set must be regularly remeshed. This is carried out using the same mapping schemes which are applied at each timestep [17]. An additional feature which has been implemented is particle reprojection. Advancing the particle field using Eq. (2.5) does not guarantee that the particle field remains divergence-free. In order to ensure this, the particle field is regularly reprojected onto a divergence-free basis using the fast-Poisson solver [18].

Turbulence Modelling A large-eddy simulation (LES) turbulence model is applied. This treats the sub-grid scale terms as an additional shear stress term in the calculation of the rate of change of vorticity - Eq.(2.5):

$$\frac{d\vec{\omega}}{dt} = (\vec{\omega} \cdot \nabla)\vec{u} + \nu \nabla^2 \vec{\omega} + \nabla \cdot T^M, \quad (2.8)$$

where T is the sub-grid scale stress tensor. The regularised variational multiscale (RVM) model is applied as described in Cogle et al. [18]. In this approach, the

vorticity field is filtered to obtain the *small-scale* (high wavenumber) vorticity ω^s field and the sub-grid scale stress is calculated as:

$$T^M = \nu_{sgs} (\nabla\omega^s + (\nabla\omega^s)^T), \quad (2.9)$$

where ν is a Smagorinski-style eddy viscosity calibrated according to [19].

Representation of lifting bodies: In order to apply SailFFish as a flow solver for the wake of a wind turbine, the unsteady circulation distribution on the blades must be resolved and this circulation must be considered in the vorticity field. An additional `Wake` wrapping class has been prepared which allows SailFFish to be coupled to an external nonlinear lifting line solver. This wake class specifies a range of important interface functions for passing and retrieving wake flow field information. For the simulations in this report, the wake solver has been configured as a `Hybrid_Wake` class, which combines a near-field filament solver with the particle solver implemented within SailFFish. This model works by storing the aerodynamic representation of the blade and near-wake filaments as representative particles at each time step. The influence of this vorticity is included in the integration of the velocity over the domain, and ignored for the integration of the vortex stretching. When the external aerodynamic solver requests velocity field information, the field is composed of the filament velocities induced by the blade and near field and the velocity induced by the particle field. Induction due to vortex filaments is desingularized using the method described in van Garrel [20]. The excitation induced by the helix method is treated simply by modifying the blade pitch with the corresponding frequency and pitch angle in the external lifting line solver. A visualisation of this is given in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. A high-fidelity simulation of the helix excitation method within SailFFish.

Solver Input and Output: The input of the SailFFish solver is specified with a text-based input file where solver parameters are specified including grid size, domain size and solver options. At each timestep, grid diagnostics are exported to a

dedicated output file to monitor flow field statistics. A summary of the input is generate at initialization of the solver for reference in setting up later simulations. This summary file is updated on conclusion of the simulation with the total simulation run time. In addition to this, at regular user-specified intervals the full vorticity and velocity fields are exported as a Paraview `.vtk` grid file for visualisation of the flow field. SailFFish has also been compiled in `.dll` with the aforementioned wake solver interface to allow coupling with external software. For the simulations conducted in this report, this was not employed. The format however has been tested and will be incorporated as a wake solver option of QBlade.

Figure 6. A range of turbine architectures which can be simulated in QBlade.

2.4.4 QBlade

QBlade is a state-of-the-art multi-physics code covering the complete range of aspects required for the aero-servo-hydro-elastic simulation of horizontal or vertical axis wind turbines. This software, developed since 2010, is implemented as a modular system of highly efficient multi-fidelity aerodynamic, structural dynamic, and hydrodynamic solvers within a modern, object-oriented C++ framework. [21]. Within QBlade currently two aerodynamic models exist for the simulation of loads acting on the wind turbine. The first is the unsteady blade element-momentum method, which treats the induction effect with indicial functions [22]. The second treats the wake with a free vortex wake model, where the wake is treated discretely with Lagrangian vortex filaments [23]. The extension with the SailFFish solver is an effort to extend QBlade such that medium- and far-wake physics can be accurately treated.

3 SOLVER VERIFICATION AND VALIDATION

In order to verify the implementation and demonstrate the accuracy of the SailFFish solver, a range of numerical investigations have been carried out. The comparisons are carried out in three stages. First, the solver is verified by carrying out a simple mesh convergence study and comparison to analytical results for a viscous vortex ring. At first, the steady velocity field calculated by a given circulation distribution is compared to the analytical solution for a range of vortex ring core radii. Following this, the unsteady development of the vorticity field as a function of time is verified by inspecting conserved flow quantities and comparing to an analytical solution. Secondly, in Section 3.2, the SailFFish code is verified against the existing MIRAS solver with the lifting-line (LL) model in combination with a hybrid filament-particle-mesh method. The rotor used for comparison are modified based on the IEA 10MW RWT [6] and in steady-state operating conditions under uniform inflow is used. Third and finally, in Section 3.3, numerical simulations will be carried out with SailFFish which replicate experiments carried out in the open-jet facility (OJF) of the Delft University of Technology (TU Delft). For the comparisons, both the quantities at the rotor (e.g. angle of attack, spanwise load distribution, etc.) and in the wake (e.g. velocity field, turbulence intensity, etc.) are used. The purpose is to have comprehensive verification and validation of the newly developed and implemented SailFFish code.

3.1 SailFFish Verification: Vortex ring flows

In order to verify the solver, simulations will be carried out for a case with known analytical solutions.

3.1.1 Unbounded Vortical Flow: Viscous Vortex Rings

A suitable test case to demonstrate the evolution of the vorticity field is a thin viscous vortex ring. The availability of analytical results for this case allow for a direct evaluation of the velocity field along with the early evolution of the flow field. Initially the kinematics of the ring and analytical solutions will be described. The steady case of the initial velocity field induced by a vortex ring will then be investigated. Following this, the unsteady case of a translating vortex ring will be simulated.

3.1.1.1 Kinematic Description

The vortex ring has radius R , coresize δ and integral circulation Γ . The initial vorticity field is specified by the following axysymmetric vorticity distribution:

$$\omega_{\theta}(r, x) = -\frac{\Gamma}{\pi\delta^2} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2 + (r - R)^2}{\delta^2}\right), \quad \omega_x(r, x) = 0, \quad (3.1)$$

where $r^2 = y^2 + z^2$ and $\theta = \tan^{-1}(z/y)$. The behaviour of the ring can be characterised by the rotational Reynolds number $Re = \Gamma/\nu$, the characteristic time $t_f = R^2/\Gamma$ and the nondimensional coresize $\epsilon = \delta/R$. As a result of the self-induced velocity field, the ring translates in the positive x -direction. The first analytical result for the translational velocity of the viscous vortex ring was given by [24] as:

$$u_S = \frac{d\mathcal{X}}{dt} = \frac{\Gamma_0}{4\pi R} \left[\log \frac{8}{\epsilon} - \beta_0 + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon \log \epsilon) \right], \text{ where: } \mathcal{X} = \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{(\vec{x} \times \vec{\omega}) \cdot \mathcal{I}}{|\mathcal{I}|^2} \vec{x} dV \quad (3.2)$$

is the vorticity centroid of the ring and β_0 is a numerical constant. This expression is valid in the small time limit as $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ and assuming that the cross section remains Gaussian to first order. In the numerical work of [25] the error bounds $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon \log \epsilon)$ derived by Saffman were found to be conservative, and the stronger bound of $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2 \log \epsilon)$ was observed. Subsequent analytical investigations by [26] confirmed these numerical results and provided improved assessments for the early time evolution of the ring velocity in the low and high Re limits [27]. For the low Re limit, the expression is as follows:

$$u_F = \frac{d\mathcal{X}}{dt} = \frac{\Gamma_0}{4\pi R} \left[\log \frac{4R}{\sqrt{\nu t_\Gamma}} - \beta_0 - 4.5 \left(\log \frac{4R}{\sqrt{\nu t_\Gamma}} - \beta_1 \right) \frac{\nu t_\Gamma}{R^2} \right] \quad (3.3)$$

where β_1 is a numerical constant and $t_\delta = t + \delta^2/4\nu$ is a modified time factor.

3.1.1.2 Numerical Parameters

The vorticity field is initialized with the distribution given in Eq. (3.1) and on the domain with extent $X \in [-b\delta, X_u]$ and $Y, Z \in [-R_\delta, R_\delta]$ where b is a buffer factor and $R_\delta = R + b\delta$ is chosen to ensure the vorticity distribution has compact support within \mathcal{D} . X_u is chosen based on the length of the simulation to ensure the translating ring and its wake remain within \mathcal{D} for the duration of the simulation. The uniform mesh spacing $h = h_x = h_y = h_z$ is varied to investigate the influence of grid size on accuracy. The particle set is advanced at each time step with a 4th order explicit Runge-Kutta scheme. The simulation is remeshed after every fifth time step and the time step dT specified such that the cumulative Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) number is below 1. The M_2 routine has been applied for the mapping of particle properties to and from the Lagrangian grid and during particle set remeshing. A fourth-order central FD scheme has been applied to calculate grid gradients. The free-space Green's function chosen for the solution of the Poisson equation on the grid has a 4th order Gaussian regularisation for consistency with the FD scheme chosen. Magnitude filtering has been applied with a factor of $f_{mag} = 1e-05$. Both magnitude filtering and particle set projection are carried out after remeshing.

Figure 7. Translation velocity of the vorticity centroid of a vortex ring. (a) Velocity as a function of core size parameter. (b) Velocity error $\Delta U_x = (U_x - U_S)R_0/\Gamma_0$.

3.1.1.3 Steady Case- Initial Ring Velocity

The initial translational velocity field of the ring as a function of core size δ will be investigated. The ring has been initialised with $Re = 100$. For each value of δ , the grid size has been set to $H = \delta/12$ in order to ensure that the core is resolved. $X_u = 2b\delta$ has been set large enough that the entire ring cross-section is contained, and a small buffer provided for initial translation. The results are compared to the expression derived by Saffman in Fig. 7 for a range of initial core sizes. It can be seen that the translation velocity behaves approximately as the analytical solution due to Saffman- Eq. (3.2), with an error which grows with increasing ϵ . Furthermore, the error in the predicted velocity aligns well with the improved error bound $\epsilon^2 \log \epsilon$ derived by [26].

3.1.1.4 Unsteady Case- Ring Evolution

The accurate time evolution of the vorticity field can be monitored by inspecting linear flow invariants. For a viscous flow field in the absence of a non-conservative forces, the total circulation \mathcal{C} and hydrodynamic impulse \mathcal{I} are conserved:

$$\mathcal{C} = \int \vec{\omega} dV, \quad \mathcal{I} = \int \vec{x} \times \vec{\omega} dV, \quad (3.4)$$

where \vec{x} is the position of the particle and the volume integral is taken over all space. These quantities can be monitored during a simulation by numerically integrating the quantities discretely over the Eulerian grid \mathcal{G}_E - these integrals shall be referred to as flow *diagnostics*. Although the integrals above are performed over \mathbb{R}^3 , the domain is chosen to have compact support of the vorticity field such the integrands in Eq. (3.4) vanish near the boundary and outside of the domain, making the evaluation of the integrals possible. This is done for the case of the translating ring for a range of grid resolutions and the results are displayed in Fig. 8. Due to the symmetry of the vortex ring, the integral of the total circulation described by Eq. 3.1 should vanish. It can be seen that the total circulation remains very near zero for the duration of the simulation for the simulated grid resolutions. The mag-

nitude of the error for the $H = \delta/3$ case suggests that the deviation is likely simply due to numerical round-off errors. It should be noted that for these simulations the solver was compiled to have double floating-point precision in order to illustrate the accuracy as these values are much larger for single floating-point precision. Inspection of the hydrodynamic impulse \mathcal{I} demonstrates that as mesh resolution increases, this value converges towards that expected for a conserved field. These results demonstrate that in terms of linear diagnostics, the solver is functioning satisfactorily. In addition to the linear diagnostics described above, two quadratic

Figure 8. Evolution of the integral circulation \mathcal{C} (a) and hydrodynamic impulse \mathcal{I} (b) for the case of the translating vortex ring for three grid resolutions.

diagnostics can be specified- the total kinetic energy \mathcal{K} and the enstrophy \mathcal{E} :

$$\mathcal{K} = \int \vec{u} \cdot (\vec{x} \times \vec{\omega}) dV , \quad \mathcal{E} = \int \vec{\omega} \cdot \vec{\omega} dV . \quad (3.5)$$

The time rate of change of \mathcal{K} is related to the enstrophy through the relationship $\frac{d\mathcal{K}}{dt} = -\nu\mathcal{E}$ [28]. This can be used as a means to track the accuracy of the time evolution of the system as described by [25]. These quantities have also been integrated during evolution of the vortex ring. The rate of change of the kinetic energy was calculated using central finite differences on the diagnostic \mathcal{K} . The evolution of the quadratic diagnostics is displayed in Fig. 9. The evolution of the quantity $-\nu\mathcal{E}$ is

Figure 9. (a) Evolution of the rate of change of the integral kinetic energy \mathcal{K} for the case of the translating vortex ring. (b) Translation velocity of the vorticity centroid as a function of normalized time.

also shown for the finest resolution $H = \delta/12$ for comparison. It can be seen that as the mesh resolution increases, the rate of change of kinetic energy approaches the expected value. The evolution of the normalised translational velocity of the vorticity centroid- $U_x R/\Gamma_0$ is also displayed in Fig. 9. The value as predicted by the original theory by Saffman U_S (3.2) for arbitrary Re is shown along with the asymptotic version derived by Fukumoto for low-Re cases U_F (3.3) for reference. It can be seen that in the low resolution case a sawtooth pattern is observed in the evolution of U_x . This is the result of both i) the particle redistribution process and ii) the mapping scheme, for both of which an explanation is readily available: When the grid resolution is increased, the time resolution must also be increased in order to satisfy the CFL constraint. As the global time constant t_Γ of the flow remains unchanged, smaller time steps between particle redistribution implies that the particle displacement on \mathcal{G}_L is decreased, explaining point i). Equivalently, an increased grid resolution also implies that error in flow field moment conservation which is incurred during redistribution (here the M_2 scheme) are reduced, explaining point ii). It can be seen that as the mesh resolution is increased, the time evolution of the U_x agrees better with the expression due to Fukumoto U_F . These results appear to be well aligned with similar investigation in the literature [29]. As the expressions for U_S and U_F are valid in the limit $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$, this error is expected to increase as t_Γ increases, as indeed is observed. These simulations demonstrate that for the case of an unbounded vortical flow, the solver is functioning correctly.

3.2 Code to Code comparison: SailFFish and MIRAS

In this section, the comparisons between SailFFish and MIRAS lifting-line (LL) module are performed for a steady-state condition.

3.2.1 Comparison setup: IEA 10MW RWT

The numerical simulations in this section are conducted using blade geometries derived from the IEA-10.0-198 10 MW reference wind turbine (RWT) [6].

Blades used for the comparison The blade's main axis is defined as its half-chord line, with all airfoils oriented perpendicular to this reference line. In the blade configuration used in this study, both the prebend and sweep are removed from the original design, resulting in a straight half-chord line. The blade length is 96.2 m, with a hub radius of 2.8 m, resulting in a total rotor radius of 99 m. To have a clear and consistent comparison, the simulations are performed with the rotor operating under steady-state conditions with uniform inflow. Furthermore, the rotor tilt, the cone angle and yaw error are set to zero, ensuring that the inflow is perpendicular to the rotor plane. Elastic deformations of the wind turbine, including the rotor and the tower, are not considered; thus, the blades are modeled as rigid bodies.

Operational conditions

The operational conditions used in this study corresponds to the optimal operational condition defined in the IEA Wind TCP Task 37 report [6], which has a high rotor thrust. Specifically, the rotor operates under a uniform inflow of 8 m/s with a constant rotational speed of 0.855 rad/s and zero blade pitch angle. Under these conditions, the tip speed ratio is 10.58, the rotor thrust coefficient is 0.90 and the rotor power coefficient is 0.46, as predicted by the BEM method.

High-fidelity CFD reference

In this study, the incompressible three-dimensional (3-D) Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) solver EllipSys3D is served as a high-fidelity reference for calculated aerodynamic loads. EllipSys3D solves the Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes equations using a finite volume approach. The turbulence closure is provided by the $k-\omega$ SST model [30], with boundary conditions at the outer domain limit following an inlet/outlet strategy and fully turbulent flow assumed throughout.

Rotor-resolved computational meshes are generated through a fully scripted, two-step procedure to ensure consistent grid quality. First, a structured surface mesh of each blade is created using the PGLW tool [31], with 128 spanwise and 256 chordwise cells. This surface mesh is then extruded radially into a volume mesh using the hyperbolic mesh generator Hypgrid [32], yielding 256 cells in the radial direction and an outer domain size of approximately 11 rotor diameters. Boundary layer refinement is implemented with an initial cell height of 1×10^{-6} m, targeting $y^+ < 1$. The final meshes comprise approximately 14.2 million cells in total. Details of the grid topology for the baseline straight blade are provided in [33].

As a steady-state solver is used, convergence can be challenging, especially near the blade root and regions of high airfoil thickness. The flow separation in these regions often resulting in limit cycles rather than true convergence. The present analysis uses the last 50 iterations for load averaging, which still have some load variations in the root region.

It is important to note that while EllipSys3D is employed as a high-fidelity tool for the comparison of aerodynamic loads, detailed wake information, such as flow field and wake statistics from the CFD, are not included in the present analysis.

Airfoil polar

The airfoil polars used in this study are obtained from two-dimensional (2-D), fully turbulent CFD simulations [6], performed with EllipSys2D and employing the same $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model as in the 3-D CFD analyses. Previous benchmark studies [34, 35] have demonstrated that the engineering aerodynamic models (e.g., BEM and LL-based methods), when using this consistent set of 2-D airfoil data, show good agreement with high-fidelity 3-D CFD results from EllipSys3D. This consistent

methodology provides a robust basis for direct comparison of aerodynamic performance between vortex solvers (e.g., SailFFish and MIRAS) and CFD in the present work.

Simulation setup in MIRAS

Within the lifting-line (LL) module in the MIRAS solver, each blade is modeled by placing a concentrated bound vortex along the 1/4 chord position, discretized into a series of vortex filaments. With the spanwise and temporal variation of the bound circulation strength, vorticities are trailed and shed into the wake.

A hybrid filament–particle–mesh approach is adopted for wake simulation. Vortex filaments are used to represent the bound vortex as well as the first two rows of the wake behind each blade, while the remainder of the wake is described using vortex particles. These particles are subsequently interpolated onto an auxiliary Cartesian grid for efficient computation. For the simulations, if not otherwise stated, the LES model is enabled.

As outlined in Section 2.4.1, the mutual interactions between vortex particles and their influence on the filaments are evaluated efficiently using a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)-based solver to resolve the Poisson equation with a regularized Green’s function under free-space boundary conditions. A tenth-order Gaussian filter is implemented for the regularization, following the method described in [10, 11]. Furthermore, a filter function with a width of 1.5 times the mesh cell size is selected to further reduce numerical smoothing errors.

The Cartesian mesh used for wake modeling extends roughly $(11D \times 2D \times 2D)$ (where D is the rotor diameter), with a grid resolution of 2 m, or about $0.01D$. This setup leads to a mesh with approximately 44 million cells with the same number of vortex particles. Both spatial and temporal discretizations are chosen to accurately capture the wake-induced effects. The simulation uses a time step of 0.03 s, equivalent to an azimuthal discretization of about 1.5° per step, resulting in 240 time steps for each rotation. As shown in [1, 2], this choice of the time step size is sufficient. Each run is conducted for 30,000 time steps, corresponding to a total simulation time of 900 s or around 122 complete revolutions of the rotor. Up to 50 sub-iterations are performed per time step, which is to ensure that the angle of attack residual converges below a predefined tolerance. Each blade is divided radially into 50 spanwise sections, using a cosine spacing for the discretization.

Simulation setup in SailFFish

The SailFFish simulations employ a Cartesian computational mesh spanning approximately $11D \times 1.25D \times 1.25D$, with D denoting the rotor diameter. The domain extends $1.5D$ upstream of the rotor to $10D$ downstream of the rotor, which should

be sufficient for wake developments. The grid resolution is set to 3.46 m (equivalent to $0.035D$), which results in a total number of approximately 15 million grid cells. The simulation uses a azimuthal discretization of 2° per time step, which is equivalent to a temporal resolution of roughly 0.04 s. Each rotor revolution therefore consists of 180 time steps. This timestep was chosen to limit the displacement of the particles before remeshing is carried out. This is reflected in the CFL parameter, which gives the convection distance of each particle at each timestep as a fraction of the cell size, and therewith ensures that the particle do not convect outside of a cells within a timestep. For statistical convergence, each simulation is performed for 21,600 time steps, covering 120 rotor revolutions and a total simulation time of approximately 882 s. For the blade modeling, the lifting-line is discretized into 30 spanwise sections per blade, using cosine spacing to provide higher resolution near the blade root and tip. All computations are performed on a GPU using single-precision floating-point data and operation, in order to reduce the memory requirements of the GPU.

Compared to the MIRAS setup, the SailFFish setup uses a slightly smaller size traverse plane ($1.25D$ versus $2D$), with a larger grid size (3.46 m versus 2 m), with a coarser azimuthal discretization (2° versus 1.5°), with fewer spanwise sections along the blade (30 versus 50) and finally using a lower-fidelity in floating-point operations (single- versus double-precision). These choices of the setup are made to balance computational efficiency with the need for accurate wake resolution within the practical constraints of the available GPU hardware.

3.2.2 Rotor aerodynamic performance

In this section, the aerodynamic performance of the IEA 10MW RWT predicted from SailFFish are compared with results from MIRAS and EllipSys3D.

Aerodynamic loads

In this study, non-dimensional axial and tangential loads, corresponding to the y - and x -directions in the blade local coordinate system (BL-sys), as defined in [36], are used for comparison. The axial force is non-dimensionalised with the local thrust coefficient (C_t), while the tangential force is non-dimensionalised with a simplified local power coefficient (C_p), defined as:

$$C_t = \frac{N_B f_y^{\text{BL}}}{\frac{1}{2} \rho U_0^2 2\pi r}, \quad C_p \equiv \frac{\Omega r N_B f_x^{\text{BL}}}{\frac{1}{2} \rho U_0^3 2\pi r}, \quad (3.6)$$

where C_p quantifies the contribution of the tangential force to aerodynamic power. Note that other loads, such as sectional moments, may also contribute to power generation; however, their impact is typically negligible for moderately large wind turbine blades.

First, loads calculated using the vortex solver SailFFish are compared with results from MIRAS and the RANS CFD solver, are depicted in Figure 10. For the thrust coefficient C_t , both MIRAS and SailFFish predictions show very good agreement with those from the CFD solver across most of the blade span. This good agreement suggests that the vortex-based solvers are accurately predicting the bound circulation distribution along the blade span. However, some deviations are observed in the root region ($r < 20$ m). Nevertheless, both MIRAS and SailFFish predict very similar results, indicating consistent modeling approaches. The differences compared to CFD results in this root region, as discussed earlier in Section 3.2.1, are likely due to unsteady flow separation effects, which are varying in time. In addition, some differences can attribute to the 3D rotational effects not included in the 2D airfoil polar data.

Figure 10. Thrust coefficient C_t (left) and simplified power coefficient C_p (right) of the modified IEA 10MW RWT blade at a wind speed of 8 m/s, calculated using the vortex solvers SailFFish and MIRAS and the RANS CFD solver.

For the simplified power coefficient C_p , both vortex solvers again show very good overall agreement with the CFD results. Notably, results from MIRAS show a closer agreement with CFD results, especially from radius between approximately 30 m and 85 m. The small differences observed in C_p may stem from differences in the numerical modeling of the vortex system, such as the bound vortex modeling and the determination of velocities at the first row of wake filaments. Importantly, both vortex solvers substantially outperform the conventional BEM method in predicting the local power coefficient. As reported previously in [36] (not duplicated here), the BEM method tends to significantly overestimate the tangential loads, because it neglects the wake-roll up and wake expansion effect. In comparison, both the CFD solver and the vortex models can well capture such effects. In summary, both MIRAS and SailFFish demonstrate strong consistency with CFD predictions,

for both local thrust and power coefficients. This serves as a strong verification of the implementation of the vortex method in the SailFFish solver.

Key aerodynamic quantities

In addition to the aerodynamic loads, this section compares other key aerodynamic parameters along the blade, as predicted by the two vortex solvers.

First, the axial induction factor at the blade (a_B) and the angle of attack are depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Axial induction factor at the blade a_B (left) and angle of attack α (right) of the modified IEA 10MW RWT blade at a wind speed of 8 m/s, calculated using the vortex solvers SailFFish and MIRAS.

For the results in the axial induction plot, it can be clearly visualized that MIRAS predicts a higher overall level of the axial induction factor compared to the predictions from SailFFish, showing an offset across most of the blade span (radius of around 20 m to 90 m). Despite this, the resulting difference in predicted angle of attack from both solvers is negligible. The angle of attack predicted by MIRAS only shows a slight reduction compared to SailFFish. Furthermore, the radial distribution of lift coefficient (C_l) and the bound circulation strength (Γ) are shown in Figure 12.

For the lift coefficient C_l , the value predicted by MIRAS is slightly lower compared to SailFFish, which is directly related to the small difference in angle of attack, as shown in Figure 11 (b). And for the bound circulation strength, the prediction from MIRAS again shows a slightly lower value compared to SailFFish, which is directly linked to the offset in the lift coefficient.

These discrepancies can be attributed to differences in numerical implementation and the specific modeling choices used in representing the vortex system in each

Figure 12. Lift coefficient C_l (left) and bound circulation strength Γ (right) of the modified IEA 10MW RWT blade at a wind speed of 8 m/s, calculated using the vortex solvers SailFFish and MIRAS.

code. However, these differences are minor and do not significantly impact the evaluation of aerodynamic performance and also shall not for evaluating wake behaviors. In addition, the consistent pattern that MIRAS predicts a higher overall induction level is observed in other key quantities shown in this section (e.g., angle of attack, lift coefficient and circulation strength). Furthermore, these small differences can help explain the minor differences in local thrust and power coefficients discussed in Figure 10. According to the Kutta–Joukowski analysis [36], the thrust coefficient is primarily influenced by the bound circulation: a lower circulation strength leads to a reduced thrust coefficient. For the power coefficient, a combination of lower circulation and higher axial induction results in a decrease in the power coefficient. These numerical comparisons are consistent with these theoretical expectations.

3.2.3 Convergence study of the flow field

Following the comparison of aerodynamic loads and key performance quantities on the blade, the wake characteristics predicted by the two vortex solvers are also evaluated. However, it should be noted that the wake quantities tend to converge more slowly and are more sensitive to simulation setup than the loads on the blades. To address this, a dedicated convergence study of the flow field is carried out prior to conducting detailed wake comparisons.

Simulation time

While results of aerodynamic loads and inductions on the blade are mostly converged after around 400 s of simulation time, the flow field requires a longer simulation time to reach reliable wake characteristics. Figure 13 presents slices of the

velocity field predicted by the MIRAS solver, at simulation times of 420 s, 600 s and 900 s, using a grid resolution of 2.5 m and the LES model enabled.

Figure 13. Comparison of the slices of the velocity field, calculated from the MIRAS solver, with simulation time T of 420 s (top), 600 s (middle) and 900 s (bottom). For the setup, the cell size is 2.5 m and the LES model is enabled.

At 420 s, the wake has already convected downstream and exits the outer downstream domain of the simulation. However, as has been clearly observed, the wake from 4D and downstream is not fully developed at this point. In comparison, for the flow field at later times (600 s and 900 s), the wake shows a more developed pattern. For these later times, sequential vortex structures, which are similar to the Kármán vortex street, can now be observed. Between 600 s and 900 s, these coherent vortex structures become increasingly unstable as simulation time increases. For a further comparison, we have also extended the simulation time to 1200 s (not shown here); the flow field is having very similar behavior as that of the 900 s, confirming that the convergence is visually achieved by 900 s.

A similar convergence study is carried out with the SailFFish solver, using simulation times of approximately 440 s and 880 s. The slices of the velocity field are compared in Figure 14.

It can be concluded that at simulation time of 440 s, the velocity field predicted by SailFFish is not yet converged. Compared to MIRAS at a similar simulation time of 420 s, it is observed that the turbulent structure predicted by SailFFish develop earlier and is more significant. Also based on the MIRAS convergence is achieved

Figure 14. Comparison of the slices of the velocity field, calculated from the SailFFish solver, with simulation time T of around 440 s (top) and 880 s (bottom).

at a simulation time of 900 s, a similar simulation duration of 880 s should also be sufficient for the SailFFish setup.

Grid resolution

For the results from the MIRAS solver shown in the previous section, the particle mesh employs a grid size of 2.5 m, which corresponds to 1/80 of the rotor diameter (D). Previous studies [9, 1] have confirmed that this grid resolution is generally sufficient for wake modeling. To further assess grid sensitivity and to reduce uncertainty, additional simulations are carried out using a finer grid size of 2 m (equivalent to 1/100 of D). Simulations with even smaller grid sizes are not pursued, since the computational cost is already considerable for grid size of 2 m. At a simulation time of 900 s, the flow velocity fields obtained from the MIRAS solver with grid sizes of 2.5 m and 2 m are compared in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Comparison of velocity field slices, calculated from the MIRAS solver at a simulation time T of 900 s, using grid sizes of 2.5 m (top) and 2 m (bottom).

Overall, the velocity fields from the MIRAS solver with the two different grid resolutions are showing quantitatively similar large-scale wake patterns. In particular, the downstream locations of where the coherent vortex structures form and where they subsequently break into smaller structures are very similar for simulations with the two different grid sizes. However, it can be clearly observed that for the simulation with a finer grid size of 2 m, the smaller-scale vortex structures are better captured, while the setup with a slightly coarser grid size of 2.5 m tends to smooth out these features, merging them into larger-scale structures. These two different setups will be further compared in the next section and the impact of grid size on the wake statistics will be further investigated.

3.2.4 Wake induction and flow fields

In this section, the wake induction predicted by the two vortex solvers are compared.

Comparison of flow fields

Before analyzing wake induction, it is instructive to directly compare the velocity and vorticity fields predicted by the two vortex solvers. For MIRAS, the results correspond to a grid size of 2 m and a simulation of 900 s (30,000 time steps). The SailFFish simulation uses 21,600 time steps for a total simulation time of 882.3 s. The velocity and vorticity fields from the two solvers are shown in Figure 16 and Figure 17, respectively.

Figure 16. Comparison of velocity field slices, calculated from the MIRAS solver at a simulation time T of 900 s using grid sizes of 2 m (top) and from the SailFFish solver at a simulation time of 882.3 s (bottom).

The velocity field in Figure 16 illustrates the wake induction of the flow both inside and outside the immediate wake region. Notably, both MIRAS and SailFFish predict a distinct acceleration region at the rotor center, shown as a red-colored region in

Figure 17. Comparison of vorticity field slices, calculated from the MIRAS solver at a simulation time T of 900 s using grid sizes of 2 m (top) and from the SailFFish solver at a simulation time of 882.3 s (bottom).

the slice plots. This is a known artifact resulting from neglecting the hub and nacelle, which allows the flow to accelerate unphysically through the rotor center. In the wake region downstream of the rotor, both solvers capture the general patterns of wake deceleration and the development of turbulent structures. Notably, both solvers predict significant wake mixing starting approximately $7R$ downstream, with generally similar patterns.

The vorticity fields in Figure 17 provide further insight into the turbulent wake structures. Both MIRAS and SailFFish predict similar scales for the vortex structures, with tip vortices rolling up and breaking down further downstream. The vorticity slices also reveal the transition from organized vortex-street patterns to a more chaotic, fully turbulent wake flow further downstream, which is clearly visible in both solvers' predictions.

An important detail is that the turbulent wake structures predicted by the two solvers visually have very similar scales. This is achieved by using the same LES subgrid parameter (used to calculate ν_{sgs} - Eq.(2.9)) $C_{smag} = 0.121$ in SailFFish to match the numerical implementation in MIRAS. This choice results in similar turbulence structures between the two solvers. However, it is important to note that according to subgrid-scale model theory, it is recommended that a lower value for the Smagorinski- subgrid parameter is used ($C_{smag} = 0.04766$) for accurate capture of small-scale turbulence [19]. Using this lower value would result in even finer-scale structures and show visually different flow fields compared to MIRAS predictions. However, in this benchmark study, the matching parameter was used to ensure a direct comparison and to verify the numerical implementation of the SailFFish solver, rather than to evaluate the performance of different choices of the coefficient C_{smag} .

Overall, the strong qualitative agreement between MIRAS and SailFFish in both the velocity and vorticity fields demonstrates that both solvers reliably capture the key features of wake dynamics and turbulent breakdown. Future work on the choice of the subgrid-scale model coefficients and the corresponding impact on the flow field predictions would be valuable for further refining the implementation of these models.

Comparison of wake induction

Due to the inherently unsteady nature of the wake, a direct comparison at a specific time step is neither straightforward nor meaningful. Therefore, the comparison is based on statistical analysis over a couple of time steps. For each time step, the velocity data is sampled at a series of 2-D traverse planes positioned downstream of the rotor. Specifically, 10 traverse planes that are placed from $1R$ until $10R$ downstream of the rotor are used, where R is the rotor radius. Each 2-D traverse plane has the same size as the vortex particle computation domain, which is $2D$ -by- $2D$ and is sampled at 64 grid points in each direction. Then, during the post-processing, the statistical quantities at each grid point is calculated, including mean velocity (in all directions) and standard deviations. For the MIRAS simulation, the data used for the statistic calculation is the last 10 revolutions. For the SailFFish simulation, the results of the last 5 revolutions are used.

The contour plots of the mean axial velocity traverses calculated from MIRAS and SailFFish are shown in Figure 18. Note that for consistency, the MIRAS results are shown over a domain of $1.5D \times 1.5D$, which is to match the setup in the SailFFish solver. Comparing the mean axial velocity fields as shown in the traverse planes, two major differences could be observed for the two solvers.

First, the MIRAS results feature a pronounced low-velocity region (indicated by a dark blue ring) at approximately $0.7R$ from the rotor center. This pattern can be observed for MIRAS results from $1R$ to $8R$ downstream the rotor. This indicates that the induction is stronger at this radial location of around $0.7R$. In contrast, the results from SailFFish do not show this pattern, as there is no low-velocity rings observed in its traverse planes.

Second, the SailFFish results start to become unsteady much earlier compared to MIRAS results. For example, it can be visualized that for the SailFFish traverse at $4R$ and $5R$ downstream, turbulent wake structures begin to build up from the blade root region. For the tip vortex, the turbulent wake becomes increasingly chaotic later, after $7R$ downstream. And when the wake convects further downstream, the wake becomes more turbulent and the root region with high axial velocity (indicated by a red or yellow dot in the rotor center) appears in the traverse planes of $9R$ and beyond. In contrast, MIRAS results show a later development of the turbu-

Figure 18. The mean axial velocity traverses of the last 10 revolutions from the MIRAS results, from 1R to 10R downstream of the rotor.

lent structure in the root region. In addition, the turbulent wake structure begin to build up more simultaneously, both becomes significant only after about $7R$. These observations suggest that when modeling the wake structure, the largest differences between the solvers originate in the root region, with SailFFish predicting an earlier build up of the turbulent wake structure. This pattern can also be observed by comparing the velocity fields in Figure 16.

It should be noted that in both numerical approaches, the hub and nacelle are not modeled, resulting in a “hole” at the rotor’s rotational center. For the MIRAS result, the flow within this central region maintains a high-velocity and the flow is thus pushed through the wake. Furthermore, the flow is with less disturbance and maintain this high speed region, until around $7R$ downstream the rotor. For the SailFFish result, the flow acceleration at the rotor center region is more pronounced compared to the MIRAS prediction. In addition, the turbulent wake structures build up earlier, which can be clearly observed from $4R$ downstream the rotor.

3.2.5 Statistics: wake recovery and wake turbulence

In addition to the mean axial velocity contour plot of the traverse planes, the wake recovery and wake turbulence intensity, which are mean wake statistics at each traverse plane, are also evaluated. The wake recovery is defined as the area-weighted mean axial velocity, normalized by the free-stream wind speed U_0 :

$$\bar{U}_{wr} = \frac{1}{U_0} \frac{U_i \Delta A_i}{A_{tot}}, \quad (3.7)$$

where U_i is the axial velocity component at each grid point, ΔA_i is the area of that grid cell and A_{tot} is the total area of the sampling domain.

The wake turbulence intensity is calculated as:

$$\bar{TI} = \frac{1}{\bar{V}} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} TKE_i \Delta A_i}}{A_{tot}}, \text{ where: } TKE_i = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^3 \overline{u'_j u'_j}. \quad (3.8)$$

Here, V is the magnitude of the total velocity vector, including all three components. When calculating the turbulent kinetic energy TKE , the first three terms in the Reynolds stress are used (i.e., the Reynolds normal stresses). Then, the turbulence intensity at each grid point is weighted by area to obtain the rotor-averaged value. Note that when calculating both the wake recovery and wake turbulence intensity, the innermost region of the traverse planes (with radius less than $0.1R$) is excluded to avoid influence from not modeling the hub region and the area extends to the blade tip, such that $0.1R \leq r_{\Delta A} \leq R$.

Figure 19. Wake recovery (left) and wake turbulence intensity (right) on the traverse planes from $1R$ upstream to $10R$ downstream of the rotor, calculated using the vortex solvers SailFFish and MIRAS. Only the data from directly downstream of the rotor is included in the calculations.

Figure 19 shows the evolution of wake recovery along the downstream distance. MIRAS generally predicts a higher level of induction (i.e., lower wake recovery) than SailFFish over most of the wake. Notably, SailFFish shows an increase in wake recovery starting at approximately $8R$ downstream, whereas the MIRAS simulation with a grid size of 2 m shows recovery beginning around $9R$. Results from MIRAS with grid sizes of 2.5 m and 2 m show similar trends, but do not predict the wake recovery at $9R$ downstream. In summary, the finer mesh provides a smoother curve that matches better with SailFFish.

Figure 19 also shows turbulence intensity (TI) as a function of downstream distance. Here, the growth in TI begins earlier in the SailFFish results (from about $6R$ downstream), while in MIRAS results, the increase starts close to $8R$. There is a lateral shift of roughly $2R$ between the start of turbulence growth in the two solvers. Apart from this offset, both MIRAS and SailFFish produce similar turbulence intensity levels further downstream, with overall good agreement in both magnitude and trend. The earlier growth in TI in SailFFish could be related to the early generation of turbulence structures in the root region, which is consistent with differences observed in the velocity and vorticity field plots discussed previously.

Overall, both solvers show similar trends and magnitudes for both wake recovery and turbulence intensity, with differences primarily in the starting position of downstream turbulence development. These findings are consistent with the qualitative flow field and traverse plane velocity comparisons presented previously, further confirming the general agreement between MIRAS and SailFFish in modeling wake dynamics.

3.2.6 Discussion

The differences observed between the results from the two solvers are not expected to have a significant impact on the predictive performance of the two models. This is primarily due to the highly idealized condition used in this benchmark study, with the inflow assumed to be perfectly uniform with zero turbulence intensity, which does not reflect realistic conditions of wind farms operating within atmospheric boundary layer. Furthermore, most of the differences arise in the blade root region close to the rotor center. In both solvers, the assumption that the hub and nacelle are neglected will lead to an artificially high axial velocity region at the rotor's center. This feature would not persist if these components were explicitly modeled.

In these simulations, small differences in the modeling of the flow, particularly near the blade root region, tend to be visually amplified, giving the impression of larger relative discrepancies. For even higher accuracy, including explicit modeling of the hub and nacelle is recommended to reduce the presence of this artificial high-velocity core at the rotor center. However, for realistic simulation of offshore wind farms, the inflow condition is typically turbulent, also with wind shear and involves complex interactions among multiple turbines. Under such conditions, the wake structure is primarily governed by the tip vortices and their downstream developments. Comparing results from both MIRAS and SailFFish solvers, it is evident that the development of the tip vortex into vortex-street-like patterns and eventually into turbulent wake structures with axial pulse patterns are both well captured by the two models. As a result, it can be concluded that both MIRAS and SailFFish are expected to deliver similar performance when predicting wake interactions between rotors in realistic wind farm simulations.

3.3 Comparison: SailFFish and OJF Data

In this section, the numerical results from the SailFFish solver are validated with measurement results of the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine [7] that is performed in the Open Jet Facility (OJF) in TU Delft. Note that since the MIRAS and SailFFish solvers have been shown to perform similarly well for the IEA 10MW RWT, the MIRAS results are not included in this section for abbreviation.

3.3.1 Comparison setup: MoWiTO Turbine

First, the setups of the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine in the numerical solver and in the TU Delft's OJF wind tunnel testing are described.

Blades used for the comparison

The MoWiTO-0.6 is a laboratory-scale, three-bladed horizontal axis wind turbine developed at the University of Oldenburg for experimental wind energy research [7]. It features a rotor diameter of 0.58 m and is specifically designed for wind tunnel

studies that require advanced control capabilities and detailed flow measurements. It was designed using the blade element momentum (BEM) method with Glauert optimization.

The rotor's rotational speed is actively controlled by regulating the generator torque, enabling accurate setting and maintenance of tip speed ratios and operating points. The blade pitch can be controlled collectively using a single stepper motor, allowing for modeling collective pitching control. In addition, for advanced control experiments, such as those requiring individual pitch control (IPC), the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine can be adapted with a custom mechanism, which enables cyclic and individual pitch control [7]. The model turbine is further instrumented to measure key operational parameters, including rotor speed, generator current, and blade pitch angles. This configuration supports a wide range of studies on wind turbine aerodynamics, control strategies, and wake dynamics.

Wind tunnel and PIV measurement methodology

The experimental data are from the openly available dataset provided on the 4TU repository from TU Delft [37]. The simulation setup is similar to the previous work [38]. Note that the article describing the dataset [37] is not yet published or available to the public. As such, some measurement setups are inferred from the dataset and the description documents in the dataset. The experimental data used in this study were obtained at the OJF at TU Delft, a large closed-circuit wind tunnel featuring an octagonal open test section measuring 2.85 m × 2.85 m. The facility provides stable and controlled inflow conditions, supporting wind speeds up to 35 m/s and turbulence intensities ranging from 0.5% to 2%.

To capture the three-dimensional structure and temporal evolution of wind turbine wakes, tomographic particle image velocimetry (PIV) was employed. Flow tracers, which are neutrally buoyant helium-filled soap bubbles, were seeded into the wind tunnel flow and illuminated using high-intensity LaVision LED flashlights. The illuminated tracer particles were recorded by four Photron FASTCAM SA1.1 high-speed cameras. Camera synchronization and timing were managed using a LaVision PTU-X timing device. Data acquisition and processing were performed using the LaVision DaVis 10 software.

The measurement data covered a total wake volume of approximately 2.6 m (stream-wise) × 0.4 m × 0.4 m (cross-stream). The data covers the region from about 1.00*D* to 5.53*D* downstream of the turbine, and approximately 0.69*D* in the other two directions. This volume was constructed by scanning and combining seven overlapping sub-volumes. The resulting particle tracks were mapped onto a Cartesian grid using a spatial bin size of 40 mm, allowing for detailed volumetric velocity

Figure 20. Experimental setup of the MoWiTo turbine tests. Labelled items are as follows: 1) PIV setup consisting of four Photron FAST-CAM SA1.1 high-speed cameras, 2) two LaVision LED lights used to illuminate the helium-filled soap bubbles (HFSB), 3) the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine, 4) a LaVision PTU-X timing unit used to synchronise the four cameras and LEDs, 5) dSpace MicroLabBox used for control and data acquisition, 6) the Quansar Hexapod, 7) the seeding rig from which the HFSBs are released into the flow coming from, 8) the Open Jet Facility.

field reconstruction. The resulting data consists of $293 \times 83 \times 83$ data points on a Cartesian grid.

For phase-averaged analysis, the data were further sorted according to the turbine azimuthal position and binned into 12 phase intervals of 30 degrees each, capturing one full rotor revolution. The PIV methodology enabled the extraction of both time-averaged and phase-averaged statistics, supporting detailed investigation of wake recovery, vortex breakdown, and turbulence development under various turbine control strategies. In this study, only the baseline operating condition, with the turbine operating at constant rotational speed and fixed pitch setting, is considered.

Operational Condition

The operational condition for the baseline case of the MoWiTO turbine has a constant inflow velocity of 5 m/s. The tip speed ratio (TSR) is set to 5, resulting in a rotational speed of 86.26 rad/s [37]. The blade pitch angle was set to the value that generates maximum power coefficient under the given TSR of 5. As documented in [38], this optimal pitch angle was determined empirically in preliminary calibration runs, with the pitch angle varying from 0 to 10 degrees. The optimal pitch angle was found to be 10 degrees and the optimal C_P was 0.27. In another work, the sweep study of rotor thrust and power coefficients of the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine

against the pitch angle are performed [39]. They showed a rotor thrust coefficient C_T of approximately 0.6 at this operational condition and rotor power coefficient C_P of approximately 0.24. Note that the zero-pitch angle in the measurement corresponds to most outward position the blades could be pitched to.

Simulation setup in SailFFish

The MoWiTO-0.6 turbine model is constructed in the SailFFish solver using the input format specified for the LL solver as described in Section 2.4.3.1. Note that for this small turbine, the airfoils are operating at relatively low Reynolds number compared to multi-MW modern wind turbines. As a result, it is important to include airfoil polars with different Reynolds number that covers most of the span. And the airfoil polars used for each section are interpolated based on the local Reynolds number of this section.

In this study, the airfoil polars used cover Reynolds number from 1×10^4 to 1×10^5 , which is tested to be sufficient. This is a challenging Re range for reproduction in numerical simulations.

Another important aspect is to set the pitch angle in the numerical solver. For the wind tunnel campaign, the zero-pitch angle is not defined in a conventional way as in rotor aerodynamics. Instead, it is defined under the scope of measurements: An experimental zero pitch position was specified and the blades were continuously pitched until an experimental maximum in C_P was reached. The ambiguity about precisely *where* this zero is with regards to the twist angles provided for the blade implies that the numerical pitch angle may have an offset to the experimental angle. So, the 10° of *pitch* in the measurement does not mean setting a pitch angle of 10° in the aerodynamic modeling.

To solve this issue, the BEM method in the HAWC2 solver is used to perform a sweep-study with different pitch angles. Then, the thrust coefficient and the blade axial induction factors are inspected. Then, it is discovered that with a pitch angle of 7° , the levels of thrust coefficients and axial induction factors have a qualitative good match with the measurements. Furthermore, a pitch angle sweep was carried out within SailFFish and this demonstrated also that the peak C_p was reached around 7° . As a result, the collective pitch of 7° is used in the numerical simulations.

Similar to the SailFFish simulation setup of the IEA 10MW RWT, a Cartesian computational mesh spanning approximately $12.5D \times 1.25D \times 1.25D$, with D denoting the rotor diameter. The domain extends $0.5D$ upstream of the rotor to $12D$ downstream of the rotor, which should be sufficient for wake developments. The grid resolution is set to $0.0175D$ (equivalent to approximately 0.01 m), which results in a total number of approximately 15 million grid cells. The simulation uses a

azimuthal discretization of 1° per time step, which is equivalent to a temporal resolution of roughly 0.0002 s. Each rotor revolution therefore consists of 360 time steps. For statistical convergence, each simulation is performed for 14,400 time steps, covering 40 rotor revolutions and a total simulation time of approximately 2.92 s. Note that the number of revolution is much smaller compared to the setup used for the IEA 10 MW RWT as in Section 3.2.1. This is because for this MoWiTO turbine, the value of TSR is only 5, which is approximately half as that for the IEA 10MW turbine. In addition, the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine is operating at a lower C_T level of approximately 0.6 with a lower level of axial induction. In comparison, the IEA 10MW turbine is operating at a higher loading with C_T of approximately 0.9, which resulting a higher induction level. This means the choice of number of revolutions should be sufficient for the rotor to reach convergence for the statistical quantities. For the blade modeling, the lifting-line is discretized into 35 spanwise sections per blade, using cosine spacing. All computations are performed on a GPU using single-precision floating-point data.

3.3.2 Convergence study

To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the SailFFish simulations for the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine, a mesh and setup convergence study is performed using three different resolutions. The configurations are labeled by the grid size in the Cartesian mesh, relative to the rotor radius R . First, a coarse mesh with a grid size of $0.1R$ is tested, using an azimuthal increment of 2° per time step and the blade is discretized radially into 15 sections. Second, an intermediate mesh with a grid size of $0.05R$ is computed, with an azimuthal increment of 1° per time step and the blade is discretized radially into 25 sections. Third, a fine mesh with a grid size of $0.035R$ is computed, also with a 1° azimuthal discretization and the blade is radially discretized into 35 sections. For all three cases, simulations were performed for 40 rotor revolutions to ensure statistically steady-state results. Note that further mesh refinement was not possible due to the memory limitations in the existing GPU hardware.

Compare of aerodynamic loads and key quantities

An initial comparison for the three resolutions is performed by comparing the spanwise distribution of the aerodynamic loads at the blades. As in Section 3.2.2, the local aerodynamic thrust and power coefficients along the blade span are compared in Figure 21.

The results show rapid convergence in aerodynamic loads: even the coarsest mesh ($dx=0.1R$) with only 15 blade sections produces loads that closely match those from finer mesh setups. The intermediate and fine mesh setups ($dx=0.05R$ and $dx=0.035R$) give virtually indistinguishable results, indicating negligible sensitivity in C_t and C_p beyond this resolution.

Figure 21. Thrust coefficient C_t (left) and simplified power coefficient C_p (right) of the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine at a TSR of 5 and pitch angle of 7° , calculated using the vortex solver SailFFish.

A more detailed comparison is presented in Figure 22, showing key aerodynamic quantities of blade: axial induction factor a_B and angle of attack α . While the

Figure 22. Axial induction factor at the blade a_B (left) and angle of attack α (right) of the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine at a TSR of 5 and pitch angle of 7° , calculated using the vortex solvers SailFFish.

aerodynamic loads show very little sensitivity to grid refinement, the axial induction factor a_B is more sensitive to mesh resolution, especially in the mid-span region. The angle of attack distributions show very close agreement for all but the coarsest mesh. Overall, the difference between the intermediate and fine meshes is minor and the finest setup with $dx=0.035R$ can be considered fully converged for both a_B and α .

In summary, this convergence study demonstrates that the SailFFish solver provides robust and consistent predictions for aerodynamic loads and key flow quantities using the finest setup with $dx=0.035R$. The results justify the use of this resolution in subsequent analyses.

Convergence of the flow field

Although the results for aerodynamic loads and blade induction factors on the blade are mostly converged even for the intermediate setup, accurate representation of the flow field would require even finer resolution to reach reliable wake characteristics. Figure 23 shows planar slices of the velocity field predicted by the SailFFish solver, with different grid sizes and simulation setups.

Figure 23. Comparison of the slices of the velocity field, calculated from the SailFFish solver, with grid size dx of $0.1R$ (top), $0.05R$ (middle) and $0.035R$ (bottom).

For the coarsest grid ($dx=0.1R$), the wake appears overly smooth: while the general features of the wake, such as the velocity deficit and the artificial acceleration zone at the rotor center, are visible. The resolution is insufficient to resolve the helical trailed vortex from the blade tip region, since the overall wake structure is overly diffused. This resolution is too low to capture the turbulent wake structures and also possible interactions between different wind turbines.

At intermediate grid resolution ($dx=0.05R$), the flow field shows more realistic wake features. The helical tip vortices shed from the blade tips are now clearly visible. However, as the wake evolves further downstream, the mesh is still not fine enough

to fully resolve the breakdown of coherent vortex structures into smaller-scale turbulence structures.

The finest grid ($dx=0.035R$) provides the most detailed and physically accurate results. The tip vortices are clearly visualized and are visible even after approximately 5 to $6D$ downstream of the rotor. Further downstream, the transition from organized vortex patterns to turbulent mixing is well represented. In addition, the smaller-scale turbulent structures and the complex flow in the far wake after around $6D$ are well modeled.

These results demonstrate that high mesh resolution is critical for accurately simulating the wake dynamics. The results show that the finest mesh considered here is necessary for trustworthy predictions of wake characteristics and turbulent mixing in both the near and far wake regions.

3.3.3 Wake induction and flow fields

In this section, the wake inductions and flow fields from the measurement data are compared with simulation results from the SailFFish solver.

Flow fields

Figure 24 presents the velocity field slices of the time-averaged data from the measurement. The top plane shows the velocity field in the $x-z$ plane (perpendicular to the ground), while the bottom plane shows the velocity field in the $x-y$ plane (parallel to the ground).

From the top plane in Figure 24, it can be clearly visualized that the velocity field in the $x-z$ plane (perpendicular to the ground) is asymmetric around the rotor center. The flow velocity below the rotor is much lower than that above the rotor. This asymmetry behavior is expected since the measurement setup involves a tower and nacelle (see [38], Figure 4). However, the tower effect is not included in the numerical model. As a result, the SailFFish simulation predicts a generally symmetric wake about the rotor center.

To minimize the tower's influence in the comparison, the velocity field in the $x-y$ plane (parallel to the ground) in Figure 24 (bottom) is used to compare with the SailFFish results. Although the tower still introduces some asymmetry, its effect is reduced in this plane. Comparing these measurement results with the SailFFish simulation, as shown in Figure 23 (bottom), some notable differences can be observed. Firstly, the simulations show an artificial acceleration of the flow passing the rotor center, as the hub and nacelle are not modeled, leading to unrealistically high velocities immediately behind the rotor axis. In contrast, the measurement results show a low-velocity region directly behind the rotor center. Secondly, the simulation results show that the wake maintains a nearly constant low speed re-

Figure 24. Velocity field slices passing through the rotor center, obtained from the time-averaged measurement data with a bin size of 40 mm. The slice in the $x - z$ plane that is perpendicular to the ground (top); and the slice in the $x - y$ plane that is parallel to the ground (bottom). The rotor position is indicated by a solid red line at $x = 0$.

gion up to about $5D$ downstream and then gradually expands. The measurement results, on the other hand, show that the low velocity region contracts at approximately $10R$ (equivalent to $5D$) downstream of the rotor. These discrepancies likely stem from two main sources. First, the artificial acceleration of the flow passing the rotor’s center in the simulations changes the wake mixing pattern, which causing increased mixing also in the center wake region. So, the mixing is transporting energy from both the inner and outer regions of the wake to the intermediate region. In the actual experiment, the mixing is mainly to transport the energy from the outer flow region into the region that is directly downstream of the rotor. Second, a small portion could be due to the turbulence introduced in the inflow and also generated due to the tower effects, which are not modeled in the simulation.

To have a further inspection, one side view of velocity and vorticity field that is plotted using the phase-averaged data at phase of 0° and also the code provided in [37] is shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25. Side view of the axial velocity and vorticity contours from the phase-averaged data at an azimuthal angle of 0° of the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine from the OJF measurement. Note that both the dataset and the plotting code are from the openly available dataset [37].

From the iso-vorticity plots in Figure 25, the three distinct helical trailed vortices are clearly visible. They correspond to the three tip vortices of the rotor.

It can be visualized that the helical pitches of the trailed vortices are having some difference. In addition, the radius of the tip vortices are also having some small offsets. This is most likely related to minor geometric differences between the three blades, such as small manufacturing imperfections. Another possible contributing factor is slight imbalances in the pitch angle settings, where one blade may have a pitch angle that is slightly different from the others. Even very small differences in blade geometry or pitch angle can become apparent in the wake visualizations. It is important to emphasize that for measurements in the wind tunnel using a model wind turbine, it is extremely challenging to have three identical blades that operate at identical conditions. Small variations are common and do not reflect shortcomings in experimental practice, but are rather a practical reality of experimental

work. While these asymmetries can have a noticeable effect on the visualization of tip vortices and possibly the local velocity fields, their impact on the overall wake development and wake statistics is expected to be minimal. We expect a slight increase in turbulence intensity within the wake may result from such pitch imbalances. However, the main characteristics of the wake dynamics and turbulent mixing remain largely unaffected.

Comparison of wake induction

Next, the mean axial velocity U_x (m/s) in the 2-D traverse planes downstream of the rotor is compared between the measurements and the SailFFish simulations, as shown in Figure 26. Results are presented for locations from $1R$ to $10R$ downstream of the rotor. Note that the data at $1R$ downstream is not available in the measurements.

Figure 26. Time-averaged mean axial velocity traverses from $1R$ to $10R$ downstream of the rotor. The SailFFish results are calculated by averaging the results in the last rotor revolution over time. Note that measurement data at $1R$ is not available.

A qualitative comparison of the traverse planes reveals the same two primary differences previously discussed for the velocity field slices. First, the artificial acceleration passing the rotor’s center due to neglecting the hub and nacelle in the simulation result in a high-velocity core at the rotor center. Second, the tower shadow effect is not modeled in the simulations, while the measurements show an asymmetric wake with a low velocity region clearly showing a tower shadow.

3.3.4 Statistics: wake recovery and wake turbulence

Next, wake statistics, including wake recovery and wake turbulence intensity, from the time-averaged data of the measurement and from the SailFFish simulations, are compared in Figure 27. Both quantities are calculated according to their definitions in Equations 3.7 and 3.8. To minimize the error introduced due to the differences at the blade root region, the data within a radius of $0.1R$ are excluded from the calculations.

Figure 27. Wake recovery (left) and wake turbulence intensity (right) on the traverse planes from $1R$ upstream to $10R$ downstream of the MoWiTO turbine, from the measurement and from the vortex solver SailFFish. Only data from directly downstream of the rotor is included in the calculations.

For the wake recovery both the measurement and the SailFFish simulation results show similar general levels around 0.64 at $2R$ downstream. From $2R$ to $4R$ downstream, the wake recovery from measurement and SailFFish are both decreasing, showing a very similar parallel trend. However, beyond $4R$ downstream, the two datasets diverge. The measurement data shows a strong recovery, with the wake recovery increasing steadily and eventually exceeding the initial value at $2R$. In contrast, the SailFFish simulation predicts a nearly constant mean axial velocity beyond $4R$, with very small wake recovery effects. This discrepancy is likely related to the presence of the tower shadow effect and the possible pitch imbalances in the experiment, which can increase the mixing in the wake.

For the turbulence intensity, apart from a single outlier at $4R$ in the SailFFish simulation results, the two curves agree very well in both level and trend. Both the simulation and measurement show a gradual increase in TI as the wake develops downstream and the slope are in good agreement.

In summary, the wake statistics from the SailFFish simulations show reasonably good agreement with the experimental data, capturing the main trends in both wake recovery and turbulence intensity downstream of the rotor.

3.3.5 Discussion

In this section, we have compared the experimental results for the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine, measured at the OJF wind tunnel at TU Delft, with numerical simulations performed using the SailFFish solver.

Direct comparison of the flow fields from experiment and simulation provides valuable qualitative insight, but these comparisons are fundamentally limited by differences in the experimental and numerical setups, especially neglecting of the hub, nacelle, and tower in the numerical model. Furthermore, small blade pitch imbalances are observed in the measurement results. Therefore, our primary focus has been on the quantitative comparison of wake statistics, specifically wake recovery and wake turbulence intensity.

Overall, the results show that the SailFFish solver is able to predict key wake statistics with reasonably good accuracy, capturing both the absolute levels and the downstream trends observed in the measurements. While some discrepancies due to modeling simplifications main, the agreement is strong enough to confirm the performance of the solver for modeling wake dynamics.

Notably, our comparison shows that neglecting the hub, nacelle, and especially the tower introduces visually significant discrepancies in the flow field. However, these features appear to have a much smaller impact on the wake statistics used for comparison.

Looking ahead, future studies should more systematically address the influence of hub, nacelle, and tower modeling within numerical simulations, especially as these effects may become increasingly important for interactions between turbines in an offshore wind farm. Improved modeling of these components would further improve the predictive capability of simulation tools like SailFFish.

4 APPLICATION

A range of scenarios will be demonstrated to illustrate the applicability of the solver to unsteady wake cases. In Section 4.1 the ability of the model to capture the wake physics of the helix method will be demonstrated. In Section 4.2 a second turbine will be modeled which is operated downstream of the primary turbine, in order to numerically demonstrate multiple turbine operation.

Multi-Blade Coordinate Transform: In the following demonstrations, a number of simulations will make use of the multi-blade coordinate (MBC) transform to induce a virtual yaw or tilt moment onto the rotor [40]. This relates the individual blade pitch signals θ_i with a constant pitch angle θ_0 , and pitch signal which induce a tilting moment θ_{tilt} and a yawing moment θ_{yaw} on the rotor:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta_0 \\ \theta_{tilt} \\ \theta_{yaw} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 \\ \cos(\psi) & \cos(\psi + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \cos(\psi + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \\ \sin(\psi) & \sin(\psi + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \sin(\psi + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_1 \\ \theta_2 \\ \theta_3 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.1)$$

4.1 Helix Excitation

The helix approach fully applies the MBC to generate a periodic excitation in both tilt θ_{tilt} and yaw θ_{yaw} moments acting on the rotor [41, 38]. In a similar fashion to the deflection of the wake caused by dynamic yawing, the helix method induces a helical motion on the wake of the turbine. The purpose of applying this excitation is to induce accelerated wake recovery with a relatively small control input. In order to demonstrate the ability of the SailFFish solver to capture the wake dynamics of the helix approach, the experimental setup of the excitation tests carried out in the OJF has been duplicated. In addition to the baseline experiments as described in Section 3.3, several experiments were carried out with helix excitation activated [37]. In order to duplicate the experimental setup the helix pitch amplitude of $\theta_{tilt} = \theta_{yaw} = 2^\circ$ was chosen and the Strouhal number of the excitation was specified to be $Str=0.25$, such that the frequency of excitation of the helix actuation corresponded to $\omega_e = 0.2\Omega$ where Ω is the rotational frequency of the rotor.

4.1.1 Dynamic Wake Behaviour

A volume rendering of the vorticity field for the case of helix actuation is shown in Fig. 28. Several difference can be instantly observed. The near wake- or the region up to 2D downstream of the rotor- can be used as the defining boundary condition for the far wake behaviour by observing the magnitude of the tip vortex. In the baseline case the tip vortex appears consistent: the distribution remains axysymmetric and the diffusion of the tip vortex occurs uniformly with wake length.

In the helix actuated case, there is a clear azimuthal asymmetry in the tip vortex and the wake already begins to deform as a result of this. Further downstream in the intermediate and far wake, the asymmetries in the near-wake lead relatively quickly to breakdown and entrainment in the helix case. The effect of the helical actuation quite visibly leads to a helical deformation of the wake. Pockets of turbulence are observed for the baseline case, however investigation has shown that these are the result of the highly unstable root vortex for this model and additionally due to the natural transition occurring at the edges of the boundary layer in the model. In comparison for the helix case, already at approximately 3D downstream a highly unstable shear layer is arcing across the wake. This axially and azimuthally distributed entrainment layer appears to greatly accelerate wake breakdown.

Figure 28. A volume rendering of the vorticity of the wake for baseline (top) operation and with helix pitch actuated (bottom).

This can be better observed in Fig. 29, where the vorticity in the plane $z=0$ is shown. The effect of the strong root vortex is also clearly seen here for both the baseline and helix actuated cases. In the baseline case, the tip vortices can still be identified up to 5-6D downstream of the rotor. In the helix case however, beyond approximately 3D downstream of the rotor the tip vortices can no longer be identified. The flow is dominated by the turbulent shear layer which are generated by the helical deflections of the wake which very quickly become unstable and cause the wake downstream to become fully turbulent. This is also visible in the length scale of the turbulent structures which demonstrate that in the helix case the flow degrades much quicker to homogeneous isotropic turbulence.

4.1.2 Increased wake recovery

As a further demonstration of the impact on wake breakdown and recovery, the x -component of velocity is visualised in the horizontal plane through the rotor hub in Fig. 31. Inspection of the mean induction in both plots demonstrates that the recovery in the helix actuated case is much quicker when compared to the baseline simulation. This shall be further demonstrated with statistically evaluated data over different wake planes.

Figure 29. Magnitude of vorticity in a horizontal plane through the rotor hub for baseline (top) and helix (bottom) operation.

Figure 30. Magnitude of x velocity in the horizontal plane through the rotor hub for baseline (top) operation and with helix actuation (bottom).

In Fig. 31 cross-sections of the flow at positions $x = 1,3$ and $5D$ downstream of the rotor are shown to demonstrate the influence of the activation of the helix actuation on wake recovery. Ensemble averages were taken for each cell over a duration of 5 rotor rotations, corresponding to 1800 timesteps and a single actuation of the full helix cycle. As a first observation, in alignment with the results of the previous sections the effect of neglecting the impact of the nacelle on the flow field is observed through the low-induction root region. In this region the velocity deficit is relatively small and the root vortex appears to persist into the far wake. A second observation is the accelerated wake recover for the helix actuated case. At $3D$ downstream of the rotor, the average induction of the plane appears to be much lower than for the baseline case and the spatial distribution of induction appears to be much more uniform, suggesting increased mixing. These effects are amplified in the $5D$ position. A third observation is the increased dilation in the shear layer in the helix case. The shear layer is seen to expand and diffuse as a combined action of the wake deflection and increased turbulent diffusion, both contributing to accelerated wake recovery.

Figure 31. Velocity of the flow field in x -direction averaged over 5 rotations at a set of different downstream positions. The rotor circumference is shown for clarity.

As a final demonstration of increased recovery, the induction and the turbulence intensity is plotted as a function of downstream position in Fig. 32. This are again ensemble averaged values in the direct wake region of the rotor $0.1r_{tip} \leq r \leq r_{tip}$. It can be seen that in the case of actuation, the wake recovers much more quickly than in the baseline case. The turbulence intensity is also seen to jump quickly after 1D downstream of the rotor and remain relatively constants, implying that turbulent effects have dominated the wake dynamics approximately 3D downstream of the rotor.

Figure 32. Combined visualization of helix traverse and turbulent intensity

4.2 Multiple turbine interaction

In this section a multiple turbines scenario will be simulated. The experimental setup described in van der Hoek et al. [38] has been taken as a reference. As with

the experimental case investigated in the previous sections, this experiment was carried out in the Open Jet Facility of the TU Delft using MoWiTo turbine models. In contrast with the previous cases, this experiment was carried out with a second MoWiTo turbine operating at a distance $5D$ downstream of the first turbine. The numerical model developed in SailFFish allows easily for multiple turbine simulations as the interface has been prepared such that each blade is treated as an individual aerodynamic body. This configuration allows for arbitrary blades, turbines, or indeed other flow elements. Two cases will be simulated in the following sections - both of these are visualised in Fig. 33. In both cases, the turbines are operated such that the results are consistent with the previous section: a fixed rotation rate of 822 RPM and a static pitch angle of 7° . The cases can be differentiated as follows:

- **Baseline Case:** Both turbines are operated with a constant RPM and pitch angle.
- **Helix Case:** The upstream turbine will be operated with a helix actuation of 2° amplitude and $Str=0.25$, while the downstream turbine is operated with a constant RPM and pitch angle.

Comparisons of the rotor loads and flow field will be made to assess the impact of activating wake excitation through helix actuation of the upstream rotor.

Figure 33. A volume rendering of multiple turbine operation. The baseline case is shown (left) along with the case where the upstream turbine is operated with helix actuation (right).

Numerical considerations: An advantage of the VPM solution method is that the introduction of the second turbine has a nearly negligible increase on the computational expense of the simulation. The domain size has not been modified from the simulation in the previous section. The numerical setup has not been changed with the exception of a single modeling consideration. The calculation of the circulation within the aerodynamics module should account for the time derivative of the blade

circulation $d\Gamma/dt$ - see Eq. (13.36) from Katz & Plotkin [42]. This has been deactivated in these simulations as the highly fluctuating velocities in the downstream region lead to unrealistically strong oscillations of the unsteady load component due to the discrete timestep size.

4.2.1 Baseline case

The natural evolution of the wake of the upstream turbine corresponds to the baseline case in Section 4.1. Naturally the second turbine influences the wake development and is expected to be heavily impacted by the unsteady and turbulent inflow. This can indeed be observed in a plot of the aerodynamic thrust acting on both turbines in Fig. 34. The transients at the beginning of both plots result from the evolution of the induction on the rotor. The thrust of both turbines can be seen to coincide until approximately 0.6 seconds, as the turbine wakes do not yet interact. Beyond this the effect of the wake of the upstream is clearly seen through a significant drop in thrust of the downstream turbine. The period necessary for the newly developed inflow field to converge is approximately another 0.6 sections, after which the average thrust on the downstream rotor remain approximately constant. The impact of the vortical structures and turbulent velocity fluctuations is seen as the downstream thrust becomes highly unsteady.

Figure 34. Time series of rotor thrust acting on the upstream turbine (T1) and the downstream turbine (T2) for baseline and helix cases.

When one inspects Fig. 31, one sees that the mean velocity acting over the wake plane position is lower than the ambient inflow which explains the lower average thrust acting on the rotor. Inspecting now the rotor torque in Fig. 35 one sees similar trends, however the effect appears amplified as the downstream turbine experiences an average torque of zero. This implies that the downstream rotor is no longer capable of generating power.

4.2.2 Helix case

Inspecting now the case of helix actuation of the upstream rotor, a clear difference can be seen in both thrust and torque of the downstream rotor. Inspecting first the

rotor thrust in Fig. 34, the impact of the helix excitation on the upstream turbine is seen through the induced oscillations of the rotor thrust. The downstream turbine is seen to have an increase in thrust of about 20% compared to the baseline case. The motion of the upstream wake can also be observed in the loads of the downstream rotor which are more irregular than the baseline case. Essentially similar trends can be observed for the rotor torque in Fig. 35, however the downstream rotor in this case is seen to be generating approximately 20% more energy than in the baseline case with full wake shadowing.

Figure 35. Time series of rotor torque acting on the upstream turbine (T1) and the downstream turbine (T2) for baseline and helix cases.

5 CONCLUSION

This report presents the work carried out within the FLOATFARM project under Task 3.1 of Work Package 3. As part of this task, a new vortex-based wake solver, SailFFish, has been developed, implemented, and released as open-source software. The solver can also be coupled with QBlade to serve as a medium-fidelity aerodynamic solver.

Firstly, the SailFFish solver is verified against the well-tested and existing solver, MIRAS with the lifting-line model in combination with a hybrid filament-particle-mesh method as well as a RANS CFD solver, EllipSys3D. The verification is performed under a steady-state condition using a modified version of IEA-10.0-198 10 MW reference wind turbine (RWT) as described in Section 3.2.1. The local aerodynamic coefficients, the local thrust coefficient and the local power coefficient are compared. The results from SailFFish show very good agreement with those from MIRAS and EllipSys3D across the spanwise sections. This indicates that the SailFFish solver is correctly modelled and implemented to predict the bound circulation and wake inductions on the blade. However, some deviations found in the root region predicted by both SailFFish and MIRAS in comparison to the CFD RANS results are most likely caused by unsteady flow separation effects which are not properly captured by the lifting line models applied. Nevertheless, both SailFFish and MIRAS show similar results indicating the consistent modelling method between both SailFFish and MIRAS. Additional comparisons on the other aerodynamic parameters along the blade, such as axial induction factor, the angle-of-attack, the local lift coefficient and the local bound circulation strength, show consistent results between SailFFish and MIRAS. In this work, the convergence investigation was performed in terms of simulation time and the size of the grid before detailed wake comparisons were made. After the convergence studies, the velocity field and the vorticity field are predicted by both two solvers using the simulation setup from the convergence studies. The results show that both SailFFish and MIRAS predict similar scales for the vortex structures, including tip vortices rolling up and breaking down in further downstream. This qualitative agreement between MIRAS and SailFFish in both the velocity and vorticity fields demonstrates that SailFFish can reliably capture the key features of wake dynamics and turbulent breakdown. Furthermore, the SailFFish solver shows similar trends and magnitudes for both wake recovery and turbulence intensity as those quantities predicted by MIRAS, with differences primarily in the starting position of the turbulence development in the wake.

Secondly, the SailFFish solver is validated with the measurement results of the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine tested in the Open Jet Facility in TU Delft. Within the validation task, the MoWiTO-0.6 turbine is modelled in the SailFFish solver using the

correct pitch angle set-up detected using the BEM module in the HAWC2 solver as explained in Section 3.3.1. Similarly to the verification process, convergence studies were performed to find the suitable size of the mesh grid and temporal resolution for the detailed validation. The convergence studies indicate that the grid resolution is critical for accurately capturing the wake dynamics and a finer grid is necessary for the accurate prediction of wake characteristics. The comparison between the simulation results from SailFFish solver and the measurement for the wake recovery and the turbulence intensity in the wake demonstrates that the SailFFish solver can capture the trend of the wake recovery in the near wake region while it underpredicts the wake recovery in the far wake region. This is probably due to a simplified simulation set-up without considering the presence of the nacelle, tower, turbulent inflow and unsteadiness observed in the experiment. These factors may all lead to accelerated the turbulent mixing and flow recovery in the wake. Nevertheless, wake statistical results predicted by the SailFFish solver show reasonably good agreement with the measurements.

Finally, two scenarios, helix excitation case and multi-turbine interaction case, have been simulated to illustrate the capability of the SailFFish solver to simulate wake excitation and multiple turbine interaction. The results from the helix excitation case show that SailFFish can capture the helical structure of the wake due to the effect of the helix excitation through cyclic blade pitch. Changes in induction and turbulence intensity in different wake positions further demonstrate the impact of helix excitation on wake breakdown and recovery. The results from the multi-turbine interaction case are then presented. This application shows that with the helix excitation the downstream rotor is seen to be generating approximate 20% more energy than the baseline case.

In conclusion, this report serves to demonstrate that the SailFFish solver can be successfully employed for the purpose of simulating multiple turbine interaction for the design of cooperate floating offshore wind turbines within the upcoming Tasks 3.2 and 3.3 of the FLOATFARM project.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Ramos-García, S. Kontos, A. Pegalajar-Jurado, S. González Horcas, and H. Bredmose. "Investigation of the floating IEA Wind 15 MW RWT using vortex methods Part I: Flow regimes and wake recovery." In: *Wind Energy* 25.3 (2022), pp. 468–504.
- [2] N. Ramos-García, S. González Horcas, A. Pegalajar-Jurado, S. Kontos, and H. Bredmose. "Investigation of the floating IEA wind 15-MW RWT using vortex methods Part II: Wake impact on downstream turbines under turbulent inflow." In: *Wind Energy* 25.8 (2022), pp. 1434–1463.
- [3] N. Ramos-García, H. J. Spietz, J. N. Sørensen, and J. H. Walther. "Vortex simulations of wind turbines operating in atmospheric conditions using a prescribed velocity-vorticity boundary layer model." In: *Wind Energy* 21.11 (2018), pp. 1216–1231.
- [4] T. J. Larsen and A. M. Hansen. *How 2 HAWC2, the user's manual (ver 13.0)*. Tech. rep. Risø-R-1597(ver. 13.0)(EN). 2023.
- [5] J. Saverin. *SailFFish*. <https://github.com/ZepSav/SailFFish>. 2022.
- [6] P. Bortolotti, H. C. Tarres, K. Dykes, K. Merz, L. Sethuraman, D. Verelst, and F. Zahle. *IEA Wind Task 37 on Systems Engineering in Wind Energy – WP2.1 Reference Wind Turbines*. Tech. rep. International Energy Agency, 2019. URL: <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy19osti/73492.pdf>.
- [7] J Schottler, A Hölling, J Peinke, and M Hölling. "Design and implementation of a controllable model wind turbine for experimental studies." In: *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 753.7 (2016), p. 072030.
- [8] H. Helmholtz. "Über Integrale der hydrodynamischen Gleichungen, welche den Wirbelbewegungen entsprechen." In: *Journal für die Reine und Angewandte Mathematik* 55 (1858), pp. 25–55.
- [9] N. Ramos-García, M. M. Hejlesen, J. N. Sørensen, and J. H. Walther. "Hybrid vortex simulations of wind turbines using a three-dimensional viscous-inviscid panel method." In: *Wind Energy* 20.11 (2017), pp. 1871–1889.
- [10] M. M. Hejlesen, J. T. Rasmussen, P. Chatelain, and J. H. Walther. "A high order solver for the unbounded Poisson equation." In: *Journal of Computational Physics* 252 (2013), pp. 458–467.
- [11] M. M. Hejlesen, J. T. Rasmussen, P. Chatelain, and J. H. Walther. "High order Poisson solver for unbounded flows." In: *Procedia IUTAM* 18 (2015), pp. 56–65.
- [12] T. Larsen and A. Hansen. *How 2 HAWC2, the user's manual*. English. Denmark. Forskningscenter Risoe. Risoe-R 1597(ver. 3-1)(EN). Risø National Laboratory, 2007. ISBN: 978-87-550-3583-6.

- [13] H. A. Madsen, T. J. Larsen, G. R. Pirrung, A. Li, and F. Zahle. "Implementation of the blade element momentum model on a polar grid and its aeroelastic load impact." In: *Wind Energy Science* 5.1 (2020), pp. 1–27.
- [14] J. Saverin. *SailFFish: A Lightweight, Parallelised Fast Poisson Solver Library*. 2023. arXiv: [2301.01145](https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.01145) [cs.MS].
- [15] M. Frigo and S. G. Johnson. "The Design and Implementation of FFTW3." In: *Proceedings of the IEEE* 93.2 (2005). Special issue on "Program Generation, Optimization, and Platform Adaptation", pp. 216–231.
- [16] N. Corporation. *cuFFT*. <https://docs.nvidia.com/cuda/cufft/index.html>. 2022.
- [17] G. Cottet and P. Koumoutsakos. *Vortex Methods: Theory and Practice*. Cambridge University Press, 2000.
- [18] R. Cocle, G. Winckelmans, and G. Daeninck. "Combining the Vortex-in-cell and Parallel Fast Multipole Methods for Efficient Domain Decomposition Simulations." In: *J. Comp. Phy.* 227 (2008), pp. 9091–120. URL: <http://hdl.handle.net/2078.1/5211>.
- [19] R. Cocle, L. Bricteux, and G. Winckelmans. "Scale dependence and asymptotic very high Reynolds number spectral behavior of multiscale subgrid models." In: *Physics of Fluids* 21.8 (Aug. 2009), p. 085101. ISSN: 1070-6631. eprint: https://pubs.aip.org/aip/pof/article-pdf/doi/10.1063/1.3194302/15731900/085101_1_online.pdf. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3194302>.
- [20] A. Van Garrel. *Development of a Wind Turbine Aerodynamics Simulation Module*. 2003.
- [21] D. Marten. "QBlade: a modern tool for the aeroelastic simulation of wind turbines." Doctoral Thesis. Technische Universität Berlin, 2020. URL: <https://doi.org/10.14279/depositonce-10646>.
- [22] H. A. Madsen, T. J. Larsen, G. R. Pirrung, A. Li, and F. Zahle. "Implementation of the blade element momentum model on a polar grid and its aeroelastic load impact." In: *Wind Energy Science* 5.1 (2020), pp. 1–27. URL: <https://wes.copernicus.org/articles/5/1/2020/>.
- [23] *Implementation, Optimization and Validation of a Nonlinear Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake Module Within the Wind Turbine Simulation Code QBlade*. Vol. Volume 9: Oil and Gas Applications; Supercritical CO2 Power Cycles; Wind Energy. Turbo Expo. June 2015, V009T46A019. eprint: <https://asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/GT/proceedings-pdf/GT2015/56802/V009T46A019/4239069/v009t46a019-gt2015-43265.pdf>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2015-43265>.
- [24] P. G. Saffman. "The Velocity of Viscous Vortex Rings." In: *Studies in Applied Mathematics* 49.4 (1970), pp. 371–380. eprint: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/sapm1970494371>. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/sapm1970494371>.

- [25] S. Stanaway, B. J. Cantwell, and P. R. Spalart. "A numerical study of viscous vortex rings using a spectral method." In: 1988. URL: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:117188292>.
- [26] Y. Fukumoto and H. Moffatt. "Motion and expansion of a viscous vortex ring. Part 1. A higher-order asymptotic formula for the velocity." In: *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* 417 (2000), pp. 1–45.
- [27] Y. Fukumoto. "Global time evolution of viscous vortex rings." In: *Theoretical and Computational Fluid Dynamics* 24 (2009), pp. 335–347. URL: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:122473605>.
- [28] H. Lamb. *Hydrodynamics*. ISBN 9780521458689. Dover Books on Physics, 1945.
- [29] S. Liska and T. Colonius. "A fast lattice Green's function method for solving viscous incompressible flows on unbounded domains." In: *Journal of Computational Physics* 316 (Dec. 2015).
- [30] F. R. Menter. "Two-equation eddy-viscosity turbulence models for engineering applications." In: *AIAA Journal* 32.8 (1994), pp. 1598–1605. ISSN: 0001-1452.
- [31] F. Zahle. *Parametric Geometry Library (PGL)*. Tech. rep. <https://gitlab.windenergy.dtu.dk/frza/PGL> (last access: 14 February 2025). DTU Wind Energy, 2019.
- [32] N. N. Sørensen. *HypGrid2D a 2-D Mesh Generator*. Risø-R- 1035-(EN). Roskilde, Denmark: Risø National Laboratory, 1998.
- [33] A. Li, M. Gaunaa, G. R. Pirrung, and S. G. Horcas. "A computationally efficient engineering aerodynamic model for non-planar wind turbine rotors." In: *Wind Energy Science* 7.1 (2022), pp. 75–104.
- [34] S. G. Horcas, N. Ramos-García, A. Li, G. Pirrung, and T. Barlas. "Comparison of aerodynamic models for horizontal axis wind turbine blades accounting for curved tip shapes." In: *Wind Energy* 26.1 (2023), pp. 5–22.
- [35] F. Zahle, A. Li, K. Lønbæk, N. N. Sørensen, and R. Riva. "Multi-fidelity, steady-state aeroelastic modelling of a 22-megawatt wind turbine." In: *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 2767.2 (2024), p. 022065.
- [36] A. Li, M. Gaunaa, G. R. Pirrung, and K. Lønbæk. "How does the blade element momentum method see swept or prebent blades?" In: *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 2767.2 (2024), p. 022033.
- [37] D. van den Berg and D. van der Hoek. *Wind Tunnel Data accompanying the publication: Phase-controlling the motion of floating wind turbines to reduce wake interactions*. en. 2024. URL: <https://data.4tu.nl/datasets/a8555119-db46-4ecd-9138-8785b9080ff0/1>.
- [38] D. van der Hoek, B. V. den Abbeele, C. Simao Ferreira, and J.-W. van Wingerden. "Maximizing wind farm power output with the helix approach: Experi-

- mental validation and wake analysis using tomographic particle image velocimetry." In: *Wind Energy* 27.5 (2024), pp. 463–482. eprint: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/we.2896>. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/we.2896>.
- [39] D. Van Der Hoek, C. S. Ferreira, and J.-W. Van Wingerden. "Experimental comparison of induction control methods for wind farm power maximization on a scaled two-turbine setup." In: *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 2767.9 (2024), p. 092064. URL: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2767/9/092064>.
- [40] G. Bir. "Multi-Blade Coordinate Transformation and its Application to Wind Turbine Analysis." In: *46th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit*. eprint: <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/pdf/10.2514/6.2008-1300>. URL: <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2008-1300>.
- [41] J. A. Frederik, B. M. Doekemeijer, S. P. Mulders, and J.-W. van Wingerden. "The helix approach: Using dynamic individual pitch control to enhance wake mixing in wind farms." In: *Wind Energy* 23.8 (2020), pp. 1739–1751. eprint: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/we.2513>. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/we.2513>.
- [42] J. Katz and A. Plotkin. *Low-Speed Aerodynamics*. 2nd. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2001. ISBN: 9780521665520.

FLOATFARM

NEXT GENERATION FLOATING WIND FARMS

